

“D2.3”

***Automatic knowledge discovery system
prototype and user study outcome***

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the outcomes of Task 2.3, which aimed to establish connections between distinct report-level semantic networks to form a collection-level semantic network. To achieve this, we developed methodologies capable of comparing the structure and semantics of medical reports' semantic networks.

The result of this deliverable is a *Knowledge Graph* (KG) that represents the semantic connections, based on relevance, between medical reports and scientific literature. Additionally, we provide a search engine that enables interaction with the KG. Our comprehensive KG connects the report-level semantic graphs extracted from ExaMode reports with relevant biomedical literature. We also introduce and release CORE KG, a visual and interactive knowledge discovery system designed to assist domain experts in obtaining interconnected and relevant information across different data sources.

The CORE KG system allows users to search for detailed gene expression and cancer associations, retrieving associated reports, relevant literature, and supporting and contradicting facts. The data provided adheres to the FAIR principles, ensuring accessibility for both humans and machines.

Furthermore, we conducted a user and usability study on the CORE KG system, incorporating feedback from expert users. This study helped refine the tool and consider the different heterogeneous components of the system.

In summary, this deliverable showcases the successful creation of the comprehensive Knowledge Graph for computational pathology, and the release of the CORE KG system, a valuable tool for knowledge discovery in the computational pathology domain.

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List of abbreviations

AOEC	Gravina Hospital Caltagirone ASP
CCS	Change of Cancer Status
CGE	Change of Gene Expression
CORE	Collaborative Oriented Relation Extraction
CUI	Concept Unique Identifier
GCI	Gene-Cancer Interaction
IE	Information Extraction
KB	Knowledge Base
KG	Knowledge Graph
KGC	Knowledge Graph Construction
KGE	Knowledge Graph Embedding
ML	Machine Learning
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NERD	Named Entity Recognition and Disambiguation
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RE	Relation Extraction
RUMC	Radboud University Medical Center
SKET	Semantic Knowledge Extractor Tool
SUS	System Usability Scale

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the outcomes of Task 2.3, which aimed to establish connections between distinct semantic networks at the report level and create a unified semantic network at the collection level. Our objective was to link related medical reports by developing methods capable of comparing the structure and meaning of their semantic networks.

In *Section 2*, we outline the process of constructing report-level semantic graphs from the ExaMode reports for the four specific use-cases. We provide a brief overview of the SKET tool, which was previously described in D2.1, and discuss its updates and extensions to include the Celiac Disease use-case, ensuring coverage of all ExaMode use-cases. Furthermore, we showcase several examples of the semantic graphs extracted by SKET for each of the project's use-cases.

In *Section 3*, we introduce the Collaborative Oriented Relation Extraction (CORE) system, a Knowledge Graph Construction (KGC) system that combines automated Machine Learning (ML) methods with input from domain experts. The architecture of CORE is designed to be seamless, transparent, and modular, allowing easy integration of different components. The CORE system combines automated ML methods with domain experts' input, employing active learning to bootstrap a Knowledge Graph (KG) focused on *gene expression-cancer* associations. The iterative process of testing, annotation, and re-training ensures the generation of high-quality data and enables the creation of updated versions of the KG.

In *Section 4*, we present an extensive experiment to quantify the extracted knowledge and evaluate the Relation Extraction (RE) methods employed in building the KG. Furthermore, we incorporated the report-level semantic graphs generated by the SKET tool, which extracts semantic information from medical reports. These report-level semantic graphs are seamlessly integrated into the construction process of the final KG. By combining the results of our experiments, the evaluation of RE methods, and the incorporation of report-level semantic graphs, we successfully build a KG that captures and represents gene expression-cancer associations in a meaningful and informative manner.

In *Section 5*, we introduce advanced link prediction methods aimed at expanding the CORE KG by identifying previously unknown potential associations between genes and diseases. These methods leverage a given set of known relations between genes, proteins, and diseases. While it is possible to address this problem by solely relying on known associations between genes and diseases, disregarding the involvement of proteins, such an approach would overlook the valuable properties offered by gene products, specifically proteins. Recognizing the significance of these properties, we opt to incorporate proteins and their corresponding relations into the KG. By including proteins and their associated relations, we enhance the predictive capabilities of the link prediction methods. This comprehensive approach ensures that the CORE KG captures the essential properties and relationships of genes, proteins, and diseases, enabling the identification of novel potential associations between genes and diseases based on the existing knowledge within the KG.

In *Section 6*, we demonstrate the practical utility and accessibility of the CORE KG for domain experts. We provide two means of accessing and utilizing the KB: through SPARQL queries and via an interactive visual system. These options offer flexible and user-friendly ways to explore and interact with the CORE KG. Furthermore, we showcase the richness of the data contained within the KB by highlighting interesting examples. This demonstrates the vast potential of the KB and the capabilities of the released system. It is worth noting that the CORE KG is a comprehensive resource and represents the largest available KB specifically focused on fine-grained gene expression-cancer associations. The data contained within the KB is supported by authoritative literature, ensuring its reliability and accuracy.

In *Section 7*, we present the results of a user and usability study conducted on the CORE system. The findings of this study are highly promising, indicating a positive outlook for the future reuse and dissemination of the ExaMode project's results. The study underscores the value and effectiveness of

the CORE system, further validating its potential impact in the scientific community and beyond. Finally, in *Section 8*, we draw some conclusions.

2 Report-level semantic graphs

2.1 Semantic graphs construction

To construct report-level semantic graphs, we employed the Semantic Knowledge Extractor Tool (SKET) [Marchesin et al., 2022]. SKET uses Information Extraction (IE) techniques to extract medical knowledge from medical reports and links such knowledge to the ExaMode ontology (<http://examode.dei.unipd.it/ontology/>). The ExaMode ontology defines crucial concepts and properties for modeling the diagnosis of specific diseases, the anatomical location of the disease, the procedure employed for tissue analysis, and the tests conducted on the tissue itself. It is a comprehensive ontology built upon existing widely used ontologies, incorporating additional classes and relationships to seamlessly integrate with them. Whenever necessary, ExaMode defines its own classes and terms that are not available in other well-known public ontologies.

To generate the report-level semantic graphs, SKET employs four sequential components: (1) machine translation, (2) named entity recognition, (3) entity linking, and (4) graph creation. When provided with a batch of medical reports, SKET selects the relevant fields required for knowledge extraction and processes them to obtain semantic graphs, with one graph corresponding to each input report. For AOEC/ASP reports, SKET considers report fields such as TESTODIAGNOSI, MATERIALE, SNOMEDDIAGNOSI, SNOMEDPROCEDURA, SNOMEDTOPOGRAFIA, DATAORAFINEVALIDAZONIE, and SESSO. In the case of RUMC reports, SKET only considers the CONCLUSION field, which represents the pathologist's final diagnosis based on various medical analyses conducted, in an unstructured format.

Therefore, using the linked entities from a target medical report, SKET constructs report-level semantic graphs by leveraging these entities and the semantic relations stored within the ExaMode ontology. These graphs are represented in the Resource Description Framework (RDF) format. RDF is the de facto standard for expressing information in a machine-readable format on the Web. It employs subject-predicate-object triples to represent statements or assertions about resources.

In report-level semantic graphs, the entities extracted from the reports are represented as nodes in the graph, and the relationships between these entities are represented as edges or links connecting the nodes. The nodes in the graph correspond to specific medical concepts, such as diseases, anatomical locations, diagnostic procedures, and test results. The semantic relations defined in the ExaMode ontology provide the contextual information and connections between these entities. These relations help to capture the relationships between different concepts and facilitate reasoning and analysis over the underlying reports content.

Hence, by constructing report-level semantic graphs, SKET enables a more structured and standardized representation of the information contained within medical reports. This facilitates further analysis, reasoning, and search over medical reports for the considered use cases.

For a more comprehensive understanding of SKET, the ExaMode ontology, and the structure of medical reports, please refer to D2.1 available at:

https://wiki.examode.eu/images/4/4e/Deliverable_2.1_final.pdf

2.2 Semantic graphs analysis

We applied SKET to all the available medical reports from AOEC/ASP and RUMC medical centers. The total number of semantic graphs, divided by medical center and use case, can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Semantic graphs statistics. For each considered medical center and use case, we report the number of report-level semantic graphs. The -- symbol indicates that the medical center did not share data about the specific use case.

Medical Center	Colon	Cervix	Lung	Celiac
AOEC/ASP	4,102	3,683	2,137	1,888
RUMC	3,683	5,861	--	962

Below, we provide a visual representation for four example report-level semantic graphs, each of which describes one of the four considered use cases. Similar visual representations can be obtained via ExaNet [Marchesin et al.; 2022, Giachelle et al.; 2021], a visual application that allows users (e.g., experts and pathologists) to explore the report-level semantic graphs by using an interactive graph visualization tool. The interested reader can find all the information about ExaNet in D2.1 (https://wiki.examode.eu/images/4/4e/Deliverable_2.1_final.pdf).

2.2.1 Example 1: Colon cancer report-level semantic graph

Figure 1: Colon cancer report-level semantic graph.

Figure 1 presents a report-level semantic graph for an example colon cancer report. In the graph, a specific colon clinical case report (individual “exa:report_colon1”), an outcome (individual “exa:outcome_colon1”), and an intervention (individual “exa:intervention_colon1”) are instantiated. From the diagnosis, the specimen tested positive for tubular adenoma. Thus the specific outcome is an instance of the class “exa:ColonTubulovillousAdenoma”. The adenoma also has low grade dysplasia, thus SKET links the specific outcome with the instance “Mild Colon Dysplasia”. Finally, the specimen was retrieved through a colon biopsy located in the transverse colon, thus SKET stores the type of intervention using the object property “exa:interventionType” pointing at “Colon Biopsy”. The location information is embedded using the object property “exa:hasLocation” pointing at “Transverse Colon”.

2.2.2 Example 2: Cervix cancer report-level semantic graph

Figure 2: Cervix cancer report-level semantic graph.

Figure 2 presents a report-level semantic graph for an example cervix cancer report. In the graph, a specific cervix clinical case (individual “exa:report_cervix1”), an outcome (individual “exa:outcome_cervix1”), and an intervention (individual “exa:intervention_cervix1”) are instantiated. The diagnosis was inconclusive, thus the specific outcome is an instance of the class “exa:InconclusiveOutcome”. Specifically, the result was inconclusive due to insufficient material, thus SKET links the specific outcome with the named individual “exa:insufficientMaterial” using the object property “exa:inconclusiveType”. Finally, the specimen was retrieved through a cervix biopsy with no additional information about the location, thus SKET stores the type of intervention using the object property “exa:interventionType” pointing at “Cervical Biopsy”.

2.2.3 Example 3: Lung cancer report-level semantic graph

Figure 3: Lung cancer report-level semantic graph.

Figure 3 presents a report-level semantic graph for an example lung cancer report. In the graph, a specific lung clinical case (individual “`exa:report_lung1`”), an outcome (individual “`exa:outcome_lung1`”), an intervention (individual “`exa:intervention_lung1`”), and two tests, (individual “`exa:test_lung1`”) and (individual “`exa:test_lung2`”) are instantiated. The specimen tested positive for adenocarcinoma, thus “`exa:outcome_lung1`” is a named individual of the class “`exa:LungAdenocarcinoma`”. Furthermore, the outcome is located in the pleura, which presents metastasis, thus SKET links the specific outcome with the instance “`Metastasis`” through the object property “`exa:presenceOf`”. SKET embeds the location information using the object property “`exa:hasLocation`”, which points at “`Pleura`”. Finally, the specimen was retrieved through a bronchial biopsy located in the left main bronchus, thus SKET stores the type of intervention using the object property “`exa:interventionType`” pointing at “`Bronchial Biopsy`”, and the location information using the object property “`exa:hasLocation`” and pointing at “`Left Main Bronchus`”.

2.2.4 Example 4: Celiac disease report-level semantic graph

Figure 4: Celiac disease report-level semantic graph.

Figure 4 presents a report-level semantic graph for an example celiac disease report. In the graph, a specific celiac clinical case (individual “exa:report_celiac1”), an outcome (individual “exa:outcome_celiac1”), an intervention (individual “exa:intervention_celiac1”), and one laboratory finding (individual “exa:finding_celiac1”) are instantiated. The specimen tested positive for celiac disease (type 3c of marsh-oberhuber), thus the specific outcome is an instance of the class “exa:PositiveToCeliacDisease” and the marsh classification is stored as a data property called “exa:marshStage”, which is connected to the outcome. SKET stores the location information, i.e. duodenal mucosa, using the object property “exa:hasLocation” pointing at “Duodenal Mucosa”. In the specimen, it was also found erosion, flattening of the villi, and severe villi atrophy. SKET stores the first information by linking the specific outcome to the concept “Erosion” with the object property “exa:presenceOfIntestinalAbnormality”, while it embeds data about villi status in the specific laboratory finding instance through two data properties. Specifically, SKET sets the data property “exa:hasFlatVilli” to *True* – since villi are flattened – and the “exa:villiAtrophy” property to the literal value “severe degree of atrophy”. Finally, the specimen was retrieved through a duodenal biopsy, thus SKET stores the type of intervention using the object property “exa:interventionType” pointing at “Biopsy of Duodenum”, and the location information using the object property “exa:hasLocation” pointing at “Duodenum” (inferred from “duodenal biopsy”).

3 Knowledge graph construction methods

There is a need for Knowledge Graph Construction (KGC) systems that can scale to large text corpora and stay up to date while generating fine-grained information about gene expression-cancer associations. These fine-grained associations are essential to complement and validate experimental data, fundamental for advancing cancer research.

We present the Collaborative Oriented Relation Extraction (CORE) system, a KGC system based on the combination of automated Machine Learning (ML) based methods and domain experts’ feedback. CORE features a seamless, transparent, and modular architecture, where the different components can be easily plugged in. CORE also employs active learning to bootstrap a KG focusing on gene expression-cancer associations. To this end, CORE exploits the fine-grained aspects involved in gene expression-cancer associations to perform iterative tests that measure the reliability of the data to be stored in the KB and return small, selected samples to domain experts for annotation. The high-quality data generated by this process is then used as reinforcement to re-train the ML models from scratch. Active learning makes the CORE system suited to iterative KG versioning. Therefore, with the data annotated by domain experts, re-trained ML models are deployed to build subsequent versions of the KG.

Figure 1 provides an overview of the CORE main modules and workflows for the population of a KG. The “orange” workflow shows how the KB is bootstrapped starting from a set of sentences extracted from the literature, pre-processed by a Named Entity Recognition and Disambiguation (NERD) algorithm to extract entities (1), and then manually annotated by experts (2). These manually annotated sentences are used to train the Relation Extraction (RE) methods (3) and to populate the KG with a first set of reliable facts (5). The “blue” workflow builds on the “orange” one and exploits the trained RE methods to automatically annotate new sentences from the literature (4) and further populate the KG (5). The KG population module (5) employs the annotated sentences to obtain facts that are included in the KG only if they pass the reliability tests – i.e., facts tagged as *reliable* by CORE. Finally, in the “purple” workflow, a selected set of *unreliable* facts is given to the experts for manual annotation, thus providing new reliable sentences to populate the KG and re-train the RE methods.

Figure 5: Overview of the CORE modules for data processing. CORE consists of three main workflows: bootstrapping (orange), deployment (blue), and active learning (purple).

To show the robustness of the proposed approach, we conducted extensive experiments that highlight how CORE scales to large text corpora with little human annotations. Moreover, to evaluate the system effectiveness against the state-of-the-art, we performed a knowledge base completion task showing that CORE achieves top performances. We release the literature-derived KG with fine-grained facts about gene expression-cancer associations.

3.1 The CORE system

3.1.1 Preliminaries

Let us consider a directed graph $G = (V, E)$, where $E \subseteq \{(v_1, v_2) \mid (v_1, v_2) \in V \times V\}$ is the set of edges connecting ordered pairs of vertices. Given an edge $e = (v_1, v_2) \in E$, we call v_1 the source vertex and v_2 the target vertex. In our context, the nodes of G are entities, and the edges are the relationships between them.

Definition 1 (Aspect). We call aspect an attribute of a relationship between a pair of entities. An aspect A_i has a name and a domain $dom = \{a_{i1}, \dots, a_{in}\}$, where $a_{ij} \in A_i$ is the j^{th} aspect value of A_i . $Dom(A_i) = dom$ returns the domain of A_i .

When it is clear from the context, the aspect value $a_{ij} \in A_i$ is referred to as a_j .

Example 1. Let us consider the context of gene-cancer associations, where there are three aspects describing a possible relationship (e) between gene (v_1) and cancer (v_2): the Change of Gene Expression (CGE), the Change of Cancer Status (CCS), and the Gene-Cancer Interaction (GCI). Following Definition 1, CGE, CCS, and GCI are the names of the aspects with the following domains: $Dom(CGE) = \{up, down, notinf\}$, $Dom(CCS) = \{progression, regression, notinf\}$, and $Dom(GCI) = \{causality, correlation, notinf\}$. Table 2: Description of the aspects involved in gene expression-cancer associations. For each aspect, we report its domain values and the corresponding descriptions.

Aspect	Value	Description
Change of Gene Expression (CGE)	<i>up</i>	The expression of a gene is increased.
	<i>down</i>	The expression of a gene is decreased.
	<i>notinf</i>	The change of gene expression is unknown.
Change of Cancer Status (CCS)	<i>progression</i>	The cell or tissue acquires cancerous properties as gene expression level changes.
	<i>regression</i>	The cell or tissue loses cancerous properties as gene expression level changes.
	<i>notinf</i>	The change of cancerous properties of cell or tissue is unknown.
Gene-Cancer Interaction (GCI)	<i>causality</i>	There is a cause-effect relationship between CGE and CCS.
	<i>correlation</i>	There is a correlation between CGE and CCS.
	<i>notinf</i>	The interaction between CGE and CCS is unknown.

provides a description of these aspect domains.

Table 2: Description of the aspects involved in gene expression-cancer associations. For each aspect, we report its domain values and the corresponding descriptions.

Aspect	Value	Description
Change of Gene Expression (CGE)	<i>up</i>	The expression of a gene is increased.
	<i>down</i>	The expression of a gene is decreased.
	<i>notinf</i>	The change of gene expression is unknown.
Change of Cancer Status (CCS)	<i>progression</i>	The cell or tissue acquires cancerous properties as gene expression level changes.
	<i>regression</i>	The cell or tissue loses cancerous properties as gene expression level changes.
	<i>notinf</i>	The change of cancerous properties of cell or tissue is unknown.
Gene-Cancer Interaction (GCI)	<i>causality</i>	There is a cause-effect relationship between CGE and CCS.
	<i>correlation</i>	There is a correlation between CGE and CCS.
	<i>notinf</i>	The interaction between CGE and CCS is unknown.

Definition 2 (Multi-Aspect Relationship). Given a graph $G(V, E)$ and a set of aspects $\mathcal{A} = \{A_i\}_{i=1}^n$, then a tuple of aspect values (a_{1j}, \dots, a_{nj}) associated with $e = (v_1, v_2) \in E$ defines a multi-aspect relationship between v_1 and v_2 .

Definition 3 (Signature Function). Given a set of aspects $\mathcal{A} = \{A_i\}_{i=1}^n$ and an alphabet Σ , we define

$$s: \prod_{i=1}^n A_i \rightarrow S \subseteq \Sigma^*; s(a_{1j}, \dots, a_{nj}) \mapsto type$$

as the signature function that maps a multi-aspect relationship to a *type* in S , called the signature set.

The signature function defines a set of mapping rules depending on the domain of interest. In our setting, we refer to the mapping rules described in Table 3. That is, we use the signature function to map multi-aspect gene expression-cancer relationships to gene prospective roles in cancer. Gene roles allow to distinguish the genes that are responsible for oncogenesis from those that are not; these are essential information for effective for cancer research and therapy design [Haber and Settleman, 2007].

Table 3: Inference rules for gene classes. For each combination of CGE, CCS, and GCI, we report the expected gene class. Gene classes refer to the role that a given gene has on a specific disease. Following [Lee et al., 2013; Lee et al., 2014], a biomarker represents a gene that exhibits altered

expression levels in cancer, but which is not (yet) identified as an oncogene or a tumor suppressor gene. The * symbols in Rule 5 means that CGE and CCS can assume any value between {up, down} and {progression, regression}.

Rule #	CGE	CCS	GCI	Gene Class
1	up	progression	causality	oncogene
2	up	regression	causality	tumor suppressor gene
3	down	regression	causality	oncogene
4	down	progression	causality	tumor suppressor gene
5	*	*	observation	biomarker

Definition 4 (Tagging Function). Given an edge $e \in E$ and the signature set S , we define

$$\sigma: E \rightarrow S; \sigma(e) \mapsto \text{type}$$

as the function tagging an edge with a signature type.

The tagging function works on the graph and associates a signature type to an edge. We use the tagging function to label edges with gene prospective roles. In other words, the graph represents gene expression-cancer associations as gene prospective roles in cancer.

3.1.2 Overview

The goal of the CORE system is to harvest facts from text corpora to populate KGs. We model a KG as a directed graph G made up of entities connected by typed relationships. Facts (or statements) are (v_1, e, v_2) triples, where $v_1, v_2 \in V$, $e = (v_1, v_2) \in E$, and $\sigma(e) \in S$.

To obtain facts, CORE collects scientific literature from different sources, identifies sentences containing pairs of entities relevant to the considered task, and extracts aspects from them. Depending on the combination of extracted aspect values, a sentence expresses a specific signature type. Note that, for a given pair of entities, different sentences can express various signature types, as we show in the next example.

Example 2. Let us consider the following sentences taken from the biomedical literature:

- A. **Colorectal cancer** (CRC) growth and progression is frequently driven by RAS pathway activation through upstream growth factor receptor activation or through mutational activation of KRAS or **BRAF**.
- B. Somatic mutations of the BRAF gene, causing constitutive activation of **BRAF**, have been found in various types of human cancers such as malignant melanoma, and **colorectal cancer**.

In both sentences, the following entities are extracted $v_1 = \text{BRAF}$ and $v_2 = \text{Colorectal Cancer}$. Considering the aspects introduced in Example 1, for sentence A we find $\text{CGE} = \text{up}$, $\text{CCS} = \text{progression}$, and $\text{GCI} = \text{causality}$, leading to the signature type $s((\text{up}, \text{progression}, \text{causality})) = \text{oncogene}$. On the other hand, the aspect values of sentence B are $\text{CGE} = \text{up}$, $\text{CCS} = \text{progression}$, and $\text{GCI} = \text{correlation}$, leading to the signature type $s((\text{up}, \text{progression}, \text{correlation})) = \text{biomarker}$.

From Example 2, we see that different sentences may lead to different signature types. In the scientific discourse, it is not surprising that there are different viewpoints and that various studies can lead to different conclusions – even in contradiction with each other. Hence, we need to consider this potential uncertainty when facts are extracted from the literature. The CORE system models this inherent uncertainty by assigning the likelihood of being true to each aspect value. This probability is based on the evidence we can extract from the literature. Given a set of sentences concerning the same two entities, the more an aspect value is consistent in the set, the higher the probability for that value to be true. Hence, we define the concepts of Aspect-Probability Set and Multi-Aspect Function.

Definition 5 (Aspect-Probability Set). Given an aspect $A_i = \{a_j\}_{j=1}^m$ such that each aspect value a_j carries a likelihood $Pr(a_j)$, we call $AP_i = \{(a_j, Pr(a_j))\}_{j=1}^m$ the aspect-probability set of A_i .

Definition 6 (Multi-Aspect Function). Let $G = (V, E)$ be a directed graph and $\mathcal{AP} = \{AP_i\}_{i=1}^n$ a set of aspect-probability sets. We define

$$\phi: E \rightarrow \prod_{i=1}^n AP_i; \phi(e) \mapsto \left(\{(a_{1j}, Pr(a_{1j}))\}_{j=1}^{|A_1|}, \dots, \{(a_{nj}, Pr(a_{nj}))\}_{j=1}^{|A_n|} \right)$$

as the multi-aspect function that, given an edge, returns the n -tuple of aspect-probability sets.

Thus, for each pair of target entities, CORE computes the probabilities for all the aspect values and combines them into tuples of aspect-probability sets – which represent a probability distribution over multi-aspect relationships. In this way, sentences serve as supporting or contradicting evidence that strengthens or weakens the likelihood of a fact. Furthermore, aspect-probability sets drive another essential aspect of CORE: the data-driven, active learning approach used to bootstrap KGs. That is, through reliability tests based on aspect value likelihoods and inference rules, the system tags facts as *reliable* or *unreliable*. Part of the sentences associated with the most “highly” *unreliable* facts is then fed to a human-in-the-loop process that reinforces the RE methods for aspect extraction.

Table 4 provides a summary of the notation defined above.

Table 4: Notation summary.

Notation	Description
$G = (V, E)$	A directed graph.
$v \in V$	An entity in the set of vertices.
$e \in E$	A relationship in the set of edges.
A_i	Aspect i of a relationship between a pair of entities.
a_{ij}	Value j assumed by the aspect A_i .
(a_{1j}, \dots, a_{nj})	Multi-aspect relationship.
$S \subseteq \Sigma^*$	Signature set.
$s((a_{1j}, \dots, a_{nj}))$	Signature function returning a signature type in S .
$\sigma(e)$	Tagging function returning a signature type in S .
AP_i	Aspect-probability set $\{(a_j, Pr(a_j))\}_{j=1}^m$ of A_i .
$\phi(e)$	Multi-aspect function returning (AP_1, \dots, AP_n) .

3.1.3 Architecture

Figure 6 zooms into the system architecture introduced in Figure 5, providing more details about the CORE modules. The first module (*module 1*) shows that the texts acquired from the literature are processed and normalized to obtain sentences, from which a NERD component extracts entity pairs. The entity-annotated sentences undergo two different processes: bootstrapping (orange workflow) and deployment (blue workflow). In the bootstrapping workflow, experts manually annotate multi-aspect relationships between the entities (*module 2*), producing a set of *relation-annotated sentences*.

The manual, relation-annotated sentences are then used to train RE methods (*module 3*) and to populate the KG (*module 5*). The RE methods are trained to predict the different aspects of multi-aspect relationships. Once trained, RE methods are employed in the deployment workflow to obtain automatic annotations expressing multi-aspect relationships between entities (*module 4*). Then, automatic, relation-annotated sentences are used to further populate the KG (*module 5*).

In the last module (*module 5*), relation-annotated sentences are grouped by entity pairs and used to generate facts. First, a knowledge enrichment component computes probabilities for all the aspect

values and combines them into tuples of aspect-probability sets. Then, a reliability testing component uses these probabilities to perform multiple tests that tag facts as either *reliable* or *unreliable*. Only facts tagged as *reliable* are used to populate the KG.

When the deployment workflow is complete, *unreliable* facts are ranked by ascending reliability score and the top- k automatically annotated sentences associated with them are re-annotated by experts – thus triggering an active learning process that reinforces the RE methods.

Figure 6: Detailed view of the CORE architecture.

3.1.4 Versioning

The active learning workflow makes CORE suited to iterative KG versioning. We define a KG version as the graph $G_j = (V_j, E_j)$ obtained after the j^{th} iteration of the bootstrap and deployment workflows. Once the j^{th} version of the KG has been deployed, the active learning workflow starts by generating the batch of unreliable sentences for bootstrapping the $j^{th} + 1$ version of the KG. The unreliable sentences are manually annotated and used to increase the size of the datasets to re-train the RE methods from

scratch, which then generate a new set of automatic annotations to be included in the $j^{th} + 1$ KG version. Hence, once the bootstrap and deployment workflows are completed, the $j^{th} + 1$ version of the KG is re-built from scratch and comprises all the available annotations.

3.2 NERD

The CORE system recognizes gene and cancer entities from text and links them to relevant and authoritative Knowledge Bases (KBs). In our setting, gene entities are linked to NCBI Gene¹, whereas cancer entities are linked to UMLS². The choice of UMLS as the reference KB for cancer aims to maximize the interoperability of the CORE system with different existing biomedical resources, such as DisGeNET [González et al., 2020], BioXpress [Dingerdissen et al., 2018], OncoMX [Dingerdissen et al., 2020], and many others. Indeed, UMLS facilitates mapping between a wide range of biomedical terminologies, thesauri, databases, and KBs – thus easing the knowledge transfer from one resource to another.

As NERD component, CORE integrates the PubTator system [Wei et al., 2013]. Given biomedical text, PubTator provides automated annotations from state-of-the-art text mining systems for genes/proteins, genetic variants, diseases, chemicals, species, and cell lines. PubTator normalizes annotated genes to NCBI Gene identifiers and annotated diseases to MeSH³ identifiers. However, the CORE system requires UMLS identifiers for diseases. Therefore, a mapping process normalizes MeSH identifiers to UMLS Concept Unique Identifiers (CUIs). Then, to restrict to cancer, the CORE system only keeps UMLS CUIs that belong to the *neoplastic process* semantic type. Once gene and cancer entities have been extracted and linked to the reference KBs, CORE splits biomedical text into sentences and keeps only those sentences containing gene-cancer pairs. When a sentence contains multiple gene-cancer pairs, CORE returns separate entity-annotated sentences for each gene-cancer pair.

Thus, the NERD component (*module 1*) takes biomedical text as input, extracts gene and cancer entities, normalizes them to NCBI Gene and UMLS identifiers, and returns sentences containing gene-cancer pairs. These entity-annotated sentences are then passed to different CORE modules depending on the considered workflow – that is, *module 2* for bootstrapping and *module 4* for deployment.

3.3 Manual annotation

A fundamental part of the CORE system concerns the involvement of experts to manually annotate sentences with multi-aspect relationships. In this work, multi-aspect relationships represent gene expression-cancer associations. For annotation, CORE adopts a common and shared schema in the biomedical domain (e.g., CoMAGC [Lee et al., 2013] and OncoSearch [Lee et al., 2014]), where experts are required to annotate sentences with three different aspects: CGE, CCS, and GCI. CGE represents the change of the gene expression level, CCS represents the change of the cancer status, and GCI indicates the interaction occurring between CGE and CCS aspects. As reported above and summarized in Table 2, each aspect can assume different values:

$$Dom(CG E) = \{up, down, notinf\}$$

$$Dom(CC S) = \{progression, regression, notinf\}$$

$$Dom(GC I) = \{causality, correlation, notinf\}$$

¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/>

² <https://uts.nlm.nih.gov/uts/umls/>

³ <https://meshb.nlm.nih.gov>

Given the huge number of sentences containing gene-cancer pairs in biomedical literature, it is not surprising that only a small fraction of such sentences actually describes gene expression-cancer associations. It is therefore essential to have a tool capable of limiting the amount of noise introduced in the annotation process and maximizing sentence utility. In this regard, the CORE system requires the annotation of an additional aspect, the Gene-Cancer Context (GCC). GCC indicates the coarse-grained association between gene and cancer and has the following domain: $Dom(GCC) = \{expression, other\}$. The *expression* value indicates that an altered gene expression is associated with cancer, whereas the *other* value represents any other gene-cancer association – including the absence of association.⁴ Thus, the introduction of the GCC aspect serves as a filter to limit both manual and automatic analysis of sentences containing gene-cancer pairs not inherent to gene expression-cancer associations. In other words, GCC is a proxy to assess sentence utility in context.

Based on the annotation schema presented above, domain experts perform multi-aspect manual annotations between gene-cancer pairs and return relation-annotated sentences (*module 2*). Depending on the considered workflow, the sentences to be annotated come from different modules at different stages. At the beginning of bootstrapping, (entity-annotated) sentences come from *module 1* as output of the NERD component. After active learning, (unreliable) sentences come from *module 5* as result of the reliability testing. In both cases, any errors associated with the NERD component are corrected too.

Once the annotation process has completed, the set of relation-annotated sentences that are passed on differs depending on the considered module. For training RE methods (*module 3*), the CORE system employs the complete set of relation-annotated sentences. On the other hand, to populate the KG (*module 5*), CORE keeps sentences where GCC annotation is *expression* and discards those with GCC = *other*. At the same time, sentences annotated with CGE = *notinf* are also filtered out to limit noise injection. The reason behind this choice is that CGE can be regarded as the main aspect driving gene expression-cancer associations [Lee et al., 2013].

3.4 Relation extraction

While domain experts represent one side of the CORE system, automated RE methods constitute the other. These methods, based on ML models, are trained to automatically annotate sentences with different aspects composing multi-aspect relationships. Once trained, the current RE methods are then used on new extracted sentences to generate knowledge and thus update the KB.

The CORE system employs different RE methods to automatically annotate sentences with multi-aspect relationships. For each aspect, a different RE method is first trained (*module 3*) and then deployed (*module 4*). Together, the different annotations compose the multi-aspect relationship. Although simple, this approach reflects the transparent and modular architecture of the CORE system, where different components can be easily plugged in and plugged out. In other words, each RE method can be re-trained – or even changed – without affecting the others.

The RE methods of the CORE system serve two purposes: classify sentence utility and extract gene expression-cancer aspects. Each method presents the same architecture but addresses a different aspect. As the underlying ML model, all RE methods adopt SciBERT [Beltagy et al., 2019], a pretrained language model based on BERT [Devlin et al., 2019]. SciBERT addresses the lack of high-quality, large-scale labeled scientific data by pretraining on scientific papers from Semantic Scholar⁵. On top of it, a linear layer takes SciBERT pooled output – i.e., the [CLS] token representation – to predict aspect values. Predictions are scores in [0, 1] for target values. The higher the score for an aspect value, the more the RE method believes the sentence expresses that value.

⁴ Note that *other* can be broken down into different and finer values, thus leaving room for the integration of different types of gene-cancer associations in the CORE system.

⁵ <https://www.semanticscholar.org>

Definition 7 (Score Function). Let A_i be an aspect, a_j one of its values, and T a set of sentences. We define $score: A_i \times T \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{[0,1]}$; $score(a_j, t) \mapsto r$ as the score function that given a sentence t returns how close the aspect value a_j is to the truth.

Remark 1. Given a sentence t and an aspect $A_i = \{a_j\}_{j=1}^m$, then $\sum_{a_j \in A_i} score(a_j, t) = 1$. Prediction scores for an aspect A_i given a sentence t are a probability distribution over the aspect values a_j .

Thus, given an entity-annotated sentence (*module 1*), the CORE system first masks gene and cancer entities with special tokens to avoid bias, and then applies RE methods to extract CGE, CCS, GCI, and GCC aspects. GCC extraction serves to assess sentence utility, while CGE, CCS, and GCI extraction to compose multi-aspect relationships. For each aspect, the CORE system keeps the value associated with the highest score. Note that for manual annotation the scores are set to 1 if the aspect value is present and 0 otherwise.

Afterwards, relation-annotated sentences where the extracted GCC value is *expression* are kept, whereas those with GCC = *other* are discarded. As in manual annotation, sentences with CGE = *notinf* are also filtered out. The retained set of automatic, relation-annotated sentences is used to populate the KG (*module 5*).

3.5 Knowledge enrichment

The relation-annotated sentences obtained from manual annotation (*module 2*) and RE deployment (*module 4*) pass through a knowledge enrichment component, which groups annotated sentences by gene-cancer pairs and generates facts. However, for a given gene-cancer pair, different sentences can have different multi-aspect annotations. This situation occurs because, in the literature, different studies and viewpoints can lead to different conclusions. To address this intrinsic uncertainty, the CORE system assigns to each aspect a likelihood to be true.

Definition 8 (Aspect Value Likelihood). Let (v_1, v_2) be a pair of entities, $T_{(v_1, v_2)}$ the set of sentences annotated with both v_1 and v_2 , and $a_j \in A_i$ the target aspect value. Then, the aspect value likelihood is

$$Pr(A_i = a_j \mid (v_1, v_2)) = \frac{\sum_{t \in T_{(v_1, v_2)}} score(a_j, t) \cdot \mathbb{1}(a_j, t)}{\sum_{t \in T_{(v_1, v_2)}} \max_{a_k \in A_i} (score(a_k, t))}$$

where $\mathbb{1}(\cdot, \cdot)$ represents the indicator function, defined as

$$\mathbb{1}(a_j, t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{|\arg\max_{a_k \in A_i} (score(a_k, t))|}, & a_j \in \arg\max_{a_k \in A_i} (score(a_k, t)) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Remark 2. Given a pair of entities (v_1, v_2) , its set of annotated sentences $T_{(v_1, v_2)}$, and an aspect A_i , then $\sum_{a_j \in A_i} Pr(A_i = a_j \mid (v_1, v_2)) = 1$.

Example 3. Let us consider a gene-disease pair (v_1, v_2) , its set of annotated sentences $T_{(v_1, v_2)} = \{t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4\}$, and the CGE, CCS, GCI aspects. For each sentence, the candidate aspect value-score pairs are:

t_1 : CGE(*up*, 0.7), CCS(*progression*, 0.6), GCI(*notinf*, 0.9)

t_2 : CGE(*down*, 0.8), CCS(*regression*, 0.9), GCI(*causality*, 0.6)

t_3 : CGE(*notinf*, 0.8), CCS(*progression*, 0.9), GCI(*notinf*, 0.9)

t_4 : CGE(*up*, 1.0), CCS(*regression*, 1.0), GCI(*observation*, 1.0)

First, sentence t_3 is filtered out since $CGE = notinf$. Then, following Definition 8, CGE value likelihoods are computed as $Pr(up) = (0.7 + 0.0 + 1.0)/(0.7 + 0.8 + 1.0) = 0.68$ and $Pr(down) = (0.0 + 0.8 + 0.0)/(0.7 + 0.8 + 1.0) = 0.32$, leading to the aspect-probability set $AP_{CGE} = \{(up, 0.68), (down, 0.32)\}$. Similarly, CCS and GCI lead to aspect-probability sets $AP_{CCS} = \{(progression, 0.24), (regression, 0.76), (notinf, 0.00)\}$ and $AP_{GCI} = \{(observation, 0.40), (causality, 0.24), (notinf, 0.36)\}$. Thus, given the fact (v_1, e, v_2) obtained for the gene-disease pair (v_1, v_2) , we have that $\phi(e) = (AP_{CGE}, AP_{CCS}, AP_{GCI})$ consists of the aspect-probability sets defined above.

Hence, for each fact, the CORE system combines CGE, CCS, and GCI aspects into the tuple of aspect-probability sets – which represents a probability distribution over multi-aspect relationships – and performs reliability tests to decide whether the fact is reliable enough to populate the KG.

3.6 Reliability testing

The facts generated through the knowledge enrichment component undergo a set of reliability tests, which are used by the CORE system to identify those facts that are reliable enough to populate the KG. These reliability tests are based on aspect-probability sets and follow the inference rules reported in Table 3 to map multi-aspect relationships to signature types. Indeed, multi-aspect relationships can be used to infer the prospective roles of genes in cancer and to classify genes into three mutually exclusive classes according to the inferred role: *oncogene*, *tumor suppressor gene*, and *biomarker*.⁶ For instance, an *oncogene* can be inferred from $(up, progression, causality)$ or $(down, regression, causality)$ multi-aspect relationships (rules #1 and #3 of Table 3). These mutually exclusive classes represent the signature set S , and are associated with edges of the KG through the tagging function $\sigma(\cdot)$.

Thus, based on aspect-probability sets and inference rules, the CORE system performs a two-stage reliability test that first verifies that facts have sufficient evidence and then assesses the degree of contradicting evidence. The two stages are divided into sufficiency and consistency checks.

Given a fact (v_1, e, v_2) , a sufficiency check monitors whether the likelihood of not-informative aspect values is large enough to undermine the reliability of the fact. The CORE system applies the sufficiency check to $CCS = notinf$ and $GCI = notinf$ aspect values. Hence, a fact fails the sufficiency check and therefore is deemed *unreliable* if $Pr(CCS = notinf) > \alpha \vee Pr(GCI = notinf) > \alpha$, where $\alpha \in [0,1]$ is a system parameter.

The facts that pass the sufficiency check are further inspected by the consistency check. Given a tuple of aspect-probability sets, associated with a fact (v_1, e, v_2) through $\phi(e)$, the consistency check verifies that mutually exclusive signature types are not similarly probable.

Definition 9 (Signature Type Likelihood). Let (v_1, e, v_2) be a fact and S the set of mutually exclusive signature types. Then, the signature type likelihood is defined as

$$Pr(\sigma(e) = type) = \sum_{\{(a_{1j}, \dots, a_{nj}) \text{ s.t. } s((a_{1j}, \dots, a_{nj})) = type\}} \prod_{i=1}^n Pr(a_{ij})$$

where $Pr(a_{ij})$ is the aspect value likelihood, and $\sigma(\cdot)$ and $s(\cdot)$ are the tagging and signature functions, respectively.

⁶ As in [Lee et al., 2013; Lee et al., 2014], a gene classified as *biomarker* represents a gene that exhibits altered expression levels in cancer, but which is not (yet) identified as *oncogene* or *tumor suppressor gene*.

Since gene expression-cancer aspects can be treated as independent events, the signature type likelihood can be computed for the gene classes. For instance, according to rules #1 and #3 from Table 3, the likelihood of the *oncogene* class is

$$Pr(\text{oncogene}) = Pr(\text{up}) \cdot Pr(\text{progression}) \cdot Pr(\text{causality}) + Pr(\text{down}) \cdot Pr(\text{regression}) \cdot Pr(\text{causality})$$

Given that gene classes are mutually exclusive, the consistency check verifies whether the class likelihoods are too close to each other. Indeed, similar likelihoods imply that a fact is supported by contradictory evidence, thus showing some inconsistency. Vice versa, a large difference between likelihoods suggests a strong tendency towards a specific gene class, and therefore a more consistent support for the fact.

Hence, for a target fact (v_1, e, v_2) , the CORE system takes the gene classes type-1 and type-2 with largest likelihoods and verifies that the condition $(Pr(\text{type-1}) - Pr(\text{type-2})) > \beta$, where $\beta \in [0,1]$ is a system parameter, is satisfied. A fact that fails the condition is therefore considered *unreliable*. In other words, when no gene class has a likelihood large enough to overcome the others by a margin of β , the CORE system tags the fact as *unreliable*. Note that the consistency check admits that only one gene class satisfies the condition.

Example 4. Let us consider two facts $f_1 = (v_1, e_1, v_2)$ and $f_2 = (v_3, e_2, v_4)$. The not-informative likelihoods associated with each fact are:

$$f_1: Pr(\text{CCS} = \text{notinf}) = 0.1, Pr(\text{GCI} = \text{notinf}) = 0.3$$

$$f_2: Pr(\text{CCS} = \text{notinf}) = 0.6, Pr(\text{GCI} = \text{notinf}) = 0.5$$

The signature type likelihoods associated with each fact, and sorted in decreasing order of probability, are:

$$f_1: Pr(\text{oncogene}) = 0.7, Pr(\text{tsg}) = 0.2, Pr(\text{biomarker}) = 0.1$$

$$f_2: Pr(\text{oncogene}) = 0.5, Pr(\text{tsg}) = 0.4, Pr(\text{biomarker}) = 0.1$$

Then, let us set the sufficiency threshold α to 0.7 and the consistency threshold β to 0.4. In this scenario, both f_1 and f_2 pass the sufficiency check, as $Pr(\text{CCS} = \text{notinf})$ and $Pr(\text{GCI} = \text{notinf})$ are lower than α for both facts. On the other hand, only f_1 passes the consistency check, since none of the signature type likelihoods of f_2 is large enough to overcome the others by a margin of β . In this regard, for f_1 , we have $Pr(\text{oncogene}) - Pr(\text{tsg}) > \beta$, which makes *oncogene* the candidate gene class for the fact. Conversely, for f_2 , we have $Pr(\text{oncogene}) - Pr(\text{tsg}) < \beta$, which provides no candidate gene class for the fact. Therefore, f_1 is tagged as *reliable* and f_2 as *unreliable*.

Algorithm 1: Reliability Testing

```

Input :fact  $(v_1, e, v_2)$ 
Output: boolean
1 if  $Pr(\text{CCS} = \text{notinf}) > \alpha$  then
2   return False
3 else if  $Pr(\text{GCI} = \text{notinf}) > \alpha$  then
4   return False
5 else
6    $p = \text{sort}([\text{Pr}(\text{biomarker}), \text{Pr}(\text{oncogene}), \text{Pr}(\text{tsg})], \text{desc})$ 
7   if  $p[0] - p[1] > \beta$  then
8     return True
9   else
10    return False

```

Algorithm 1 reports the two-stage reliability testing process, which takes a fact as input and returns *True* if sufficiency and consistency checks are passed and *False* otherwise. In lines 1–4, the sufficiency check

is performed and, if satisfied, the consistency check is executed (lines 5–10). If the fact passes both checks, it can then be tagged as *reliable*.

The facts that pass both sufficiency and consistency checks are tagged as *reliable* and used to populate the KG. Prior to population, the edges of *reliable* facts are labeled through the tagging function $\sigma(\cdot)$ with the gene class having the highest likelihood. Note that we do not claim that gene classes are definitive. Rather, gene classes – and supporting sentences – should be treated as complementary, textual evidence that strengthens the hypotheses on the expected roles of genes in cancer obtained through experimental data.

3.7 Active learning

The facts deemed as *unreliable* by the reliability testing component (*module 5*) are taken over by the active learning process, which ranks them by ascending reliability score and returns the top- k automatically annotated sentences to domain experts for annotation.

Definition 10 (Reliability Score). Let (v_1, e, v_2) be a fact, $\{A_i\}_{i=1}^l$ a subset of the aspects associated with e , and S the set of signature types. Then, by taking a specific value a_{ij} for each aspect A_i of the subset, the reliability score is computed as

$$rel(e) = -\frac{\sum_{i=1}^l Pr(a_{ij})}{l} \cdot H(S),$$

Where $H(S)$ is the entropy of the signature set S , computed as:

$$H(S) = -\sum_{type \in S} Pr(\sigma(e) = type) \cdot \log Pr(\sigma(e) = type)$$

In this work, we compute the reliability score by considering the subset of CCS and GCI aspects and by taking their not-informative values $\{CCS = notinf, GCI = notinf\}$, as also shown in Example 5.

Example 5. Let us consider two *unreliable* facts $f_1 = (v_1, e_1, v_2)$ and $f_2 = (v_3, e_2, v_4)$ and their sets of automatically annotated sentences $T_{f_1} = \{t_1, t_2, t_3\}$ and $T_{f_2} = \{t_4, t_5\}$. The not-informative likelihoods associated with each fact are:

$$f_1: Pr(CCS = notinf) = 0.1, Pr(GCI = notinf) = 0.3$$

$$f_2: Pr(CCS = notinf) = 0.8, Pr(GCI = notinf) = 0.7$$

The signature type likelihoods associated with each fact are:

$$f_1: Pr(oncogene) = 0.6, Pr(tsg) = 0.3, Pr(biomarker) = 0.1$$

$$f_2: Pr(oncogene) = 0.8, Pr(tsg) = 0.1, Pr(biomarker) = 0.1$$

Given aspect value and gene class likelihoods, the reliability score of f_1 is

$$rel(e_1) = \frac{0.1 + 0.3}{2} \cdot (0.6 \log 0.6 + 0.3 \log 0.3 + 0.1 \log 0.1) = -0.08$$

Likewise, the reliability score of f_2 is $rel(e_2) = -0.21$. Thus, by sorting *unreliable* facts by ascending reliability score we obtain the $\{f_2, f_1\}$ ranking.

Once computed, the CORE system uses the reliability score to perform uncertainty sampling [Lewis and Catlett, 1994]. In other words, CORE ranks *unreliable* facts by ascending order of reliability score. Then, the top- k automatically annotated sentences associated with these facts are returned to domain experts for manual annotation (*module 2*). Hence, in the example above, if we consider the top- k sentences with $k = 4$, the set of sentences returned to experts for manual annotation is $\{t_4, t_5, t_1, t_2\}$.

4 Implementation and experiments

We use the CORE system to build a KG for gene expression-cancer associations. To this end, we conducted comprehensive experiments to quantify the extracted knowledge and evaluate the RE methods used to build the KG. Then, we integrate the report-level semantic graphs produced by SKET from the medical reports to obtain the final KG.

4.1 Knowledge graph construction

4.1.1 Data processing

We use different resources to build the KG, which increase with each subsequent iteration of the KG construction process. Table 5 reports statistics for the resources used to build each KG version. In the first iteration (KG0), we only consider manually annotated data coming from CoMAGC [Lee et al., 2013], OncoSearch [Lee et al., 2014], and BioXpress [Dingerdissen et al., 2018]. We revised these annotations to make them compliant with the annotation schema presented in Section 3.3.

Table 5: Raw statistics for the KG versions. On rows there is, one per version, the number of raw instances considered to build the KG.

	KG0	KG1	KG2	KG3
Manual	CoMAGC (revised)	821	821	821
	OncoSearch (revised)	157	157	157
	BioXpress (revised)	74	74	74
	DisGeNET (batch 1)	–	–	250
	DisGeNET (batch 2)	–	–	–
Automatic	DisGeNET (batch 1)	–	184,859	184,609
	DisGeNET (batch 2)	–	–	184,858
	PubMed (citing papers)	–	–	–
Total	1,052	185,911	370,769	3,211,865

Then, in the second iteration (KG1), we introduce DisGeNET [González et al., 2020] data, on which the CORE system deploys the RE methods. DisGeNET collects data on different *coarse-grained* gene-disease associations from several resources and covers most of human diseases. Regarding gene expression-cancer associations, DisGeNET contains automatically extracted data that has been identified from the literature using text-mining techniques [Bundschuh et al., 2010; Bravo et al., 2015; Bundschuh et al., 2008]. For each gene-disease association, DisGeNET provides the publication(s) supporting the association, a representative sentence from each publication, the original source, as well as information on the gene and disease involved in the association. Thus, sentences within DisGeNET can be used as a high-quality starting point from which to extract multi-aspect relationships.

After the construction of KG1, the active learning process ranks *unreliable* facts and returns the top- k sentences for manual annotation. This new set of manually annotated sentences – together with a second batch from DisGeNET – are added to previously used data and employed to build KG2. In the last iteration (KG3), we collect from PubMed the articles citing those stored within KG2. Then, the CORE system relies on the NERD component to extract gene and cancer entities from titles and abstract sentences and deploys RE methods on them. Finally, PubMed and top- k *unreliable* sentences from KG2 are integrated into KG3 construction.

4.1.2 System parameters

The parameters required by CORE are the sufficiency and consistency thresholds α and β , and the number k of sentences to be returned for manual annotation during active learning. Sufficiency and consistency thresholds regulate the degree of reliability of the facts in the KG. A low sufficiency combined with a high consistency threshold lead to less facts but with a high level of reliability. Empirically, we set $\alpha = 0.7$ and $\beta = 0.4$. We set $k = 250$, meaning that 250 sentences are re-annotated after each iteration.

4.1.3 Knowledge graph statistics

Table 6 reports the statistics about each version of the KG.

Table 6: Partition, absolute, and conditional statistics for each KG version. The "partition" statistics refer to the number of manual and automatic sentences ingested in the KG.

		KG0	KG1	KG2	KG3
Partition	Manual	655	585	605	592
	Automatic	--	96,531	95,282	435,283
Absolute	Sentence	655	97,116	95,887	435,875
	Article	411	69,462	65,236	161,449
	Gene	329	9,483	9,981	21,005
	Cancer	98	1,479	1,554	1,665
	Fact	512	71,554	89,999	153,016
Conditional	Sentence/Article	1.59	1.40	1.47	2.70
	Sentence/Fact	1.28	1.67	1.56	3.10
	Article/Fact	1.09	1.67	1.56	2.10

First, we can see that the ratio between the sentences stored in the KG and the input ones decreases at each iteration. From the first iteration, where the CORE system uses the 62% of the input sentences to build KG0, we move to the 52% to build KG1, 26% for KG2, and only 14% for KG3. Such a decrease reflects the use of reliability tests and active learning, which make the system more selective and accurate. In particular, active learning leads the CORE system to refine the RE methods at each iteration, thus reducing false positives as well as *unreliable* facts as shown in Table 7 – which presents the regression statistics of *unreliable* facts. We see that the number of facts deemed as *unreliable* in one iteration decreases in the next ones, thus confirming the active learning effectiveness to reinforce RE methods.

Table 7: Regression statistics for unreliable facts at each iteration.

		KG0	KG1	KG2	KG3
Insufficient	KG0	10	5	5	5
	KG1	--	9,055	2,308	1,135
	KG2	--	--	4,515	2,452
Inconsistent	KG0	22	18	15	17
	KG1	--	6,135	3,837	3,704
	KG2	--	--	11,380	7,786

Secondly, the large number of different genes and cancers in KG3 highlights the scalability of the approach. In this regard, KG3 contains 21,005 genes, which cover the 70% of the 30,000 estimated

genes in the human genome.⁷ On the other hand, through the integration of DisGeNET data, KGs 1–3 contain most of the (known) cancer types involved in gene expression-cancer associations. Combined, this large number of genes and cancer types leads to more than 150,000 *reliable* facts.

Table 8 presents the distribution of these facts according to the corresponding signature type.

Table 8: Signature type statistics for each KG version. The statistics refer to the number of facts tagged with each of the three considered gene classes.

Signature type	KB0	KB1	KB2	KB3
Biomarker	390	59,147	69,409	105,089
Oncogene	87	8,833	13,501	35,520
Tumor Suppressor Gene	35	3,574	7,089	12,407

Finally, KG3 represents one of the largest literature-derived KGs with fine-grained facts about gene expression-cancer associations. Compared to KG3, BioXpress and OncoMX – both relying on DEXTER [Gupta et al., 2018] text-mined results – contain less literature-derived data. Specifically, BioXpress integrates DEXTER gene expression-cancer associations for 2,024 genes in lung cancer, 115 glycosyltransferases in 62 cancers, and 826 microRNAs in 171 cancers. On the other hand, OncoMX integrates 22,904 gene expression-cancer associations between 5,524 genes/microRNAs and 272 cancer types, extracted by DEXTER from 36,196 sentences in 25,860 PubMed articles. Although larger, OncoMX is still an order of magnitude smaller than KG3. Besides, both BioXpress and OncoMX only report CGE values between cancer and normal samples, thus providing less comprehensive information than CORE to model gene expression-cancer associations. A different situation occurs with OncoSearch, which contains 451,798 sentences expressing 7,555 genes and 1,717 cancer types leading to 2,295 oncogenes, 1,549 tumor suppressor genes, and 6,779 biomarkers. Compared to OncoSearch, KG3 contains less sentences and cancer types. However, OncoSearch does not perform reliability tests and therefore ingests any annotated sentence. If we also consider the facts deemed as *unreliable* by the CORE system when building KG3, then the number of sentences and cancer types becomes 1,037,845 and 1,767, respectively. Thus, KG3 integrates a smaller number of sentences and cancer types to seek for a higher quality.

4.2 Relation extraction evaluation

4.2.1 Datasets

We evaluate the effectiveness of the CGE, CCS, and GCI extraction methods using three incremental sets of manually annotated data. Table 9 reports the statistics of these aspect extraction datasets. The first dataset (*DS0*) derives from the seed batch of manually annotated data used to build KB0. The second (*DS1*) and third (*DS2*) ones integrate additional data coming from the subsequent sets of 250 sentences returned by the active learning process. *DS0* contains 1,052 annotated sentences, which increased by 23% in *DS1* and a further 19% in *DS2*.

Table 9: Statistics on the aspect extraction datasets. For each version, we report the aspect value counts as well as the total count. Between brackets, we provide the percentage increase from one version to the next.

Aspect	Value	DS0	DS1	DS2
CGE	<i>up</i>	524	604 (+15%)	679 (+12%)
	<i>down</i>	219	263 (+20%)	311 (+18%)

⁷ <https://www.genome.gov/human-genome-project/>

	<i>notinf</i>	309	430 (+39%)	550 (+28%)
CCS	<i>progression</i>	605	719 (+19%)	829 (+15%)
	<i>regression</i>	134	147 (+10%)	162 (+10%)
	<i>notinf</i>	313	431 (+38%)	549 (+27%)
GCI	<i>causality</i>	189	227 (+20%)	266 (+17%)
	<i>observation</i>	548	634 (+16%)	719 (+13%)
	<i>notinf</i>	315	436 (+38%)	555 (+27%)
TOTAL		1,052	1,297 (+23%)	1,540 (+19%)

On the other hand, we use DisGeNET to create a large-scale semi-automatically annotated dataset for the GCC extraction method – which serves as a sentence utility binary classifier. Similarly to [Marchesin and Silvello, 2022], we employ automatically extracted data from DisGeNET to build training and validation sets while relying on manually curated data for the test set. Table 10 reports the statistics for the sentence utility classifier dataset. For training and validation, DisGeNET sentences conveying a gene expression-cancer association were labeled as *expression* and those conveying any other type of association as *other*. As for the test set, DS2 sentences were used as *expression* candidates and manually curated sentences from DisGeNET as *other*.

Table 10: Statistics of the sentence utility classifier dataset. Rows report the number of instances associated with *expression* and *other* classes, respectively.

Class	Training	Validation	Test
<i>expression</i>	18,555	6,185	1,540
<i>other</i>	18,876	6,292	825

Note that we create a unique dataset for the sentence utility classifier as the method is only applied to PubMed sentences during KG3 construction. PubMed is very general and most of the sentences are not about gene expression-cancer associations, so the sentence utility classifier is critical for the CORE extraction process. On the other hand, the sentence utility classifier is not needed on DisGeNET sentences because they are of high quality, and a filtering process has already taken place before their integration within DisGeNET.

4.2.2 Setup

For training, we set the batch size to 16 and the learning rate to $2e-5$ with linear warmup followed by linear decay [Devlin et al., 2019], as suggested in [Beltagy et al., 2019]. The CGE, CCS, and GCI extraction methods perform multi-class classification and are trained using a standard cross entropy loss function. On the other hand, the sentence utility classifier performs binary classification and employs a binary cross entropy loss.

We perform 10-fold cross validation to evaluate CGE, CCS, and GCI methods. For each iteration, we train the RE methods for 10 epochs, choose the best epoch on a validation set consisting of 25% of the training folds, and report the corresponding results for the test fold. On the other hand, given the large size of the GCC extraction dataset, we train the sentence utility classifier for 5 epochs, pick the best epoch on the validation set, and report the results on the test set.

4.2.3 Results

Table 11 reports the average performances of the CGE, CCS, and GCI extraction methods on the different dataset versions.

Table 11: Average performances of the aspect extraction methods obtained through 10-fold cross validation on each dataset version.

Dataset	Aspect	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
---------	--------	----------	-----------	--------	----

DS0	CGE	0.8812	0.8870	0.8812	0.8792
	CCS	0.8593	0.8650	0.8593	0.8600
	GCI	0.8194	0.8305	0.8194	0.8212
DS1	CGE	0.8543	0.8574	0.8543	0.8526
	CCS	0.8404	0.8436	0.8404	0.8400
	GCI	0.8150	0.8269	0.8150	0.8142
DS2	CGE	0.8760	0.8813	0.8760	0.8746
	CCS	0.8481	0.8515	0.8481	0.8478
	GCI	0.8266	0.8314	0.8266	0.8259

We can see that all the three methods perform well on the task – above 0.80 for each measure – with peak performances on CGE and slightly lower for GCI. These results underline the differences between aspects, where CGE is the most explicit in sentences – and therefore easier to extract – whereas GCI is less evident – and therefore more difficult to predict. CCS extraction is in between the other two.

This experiment shows the effectiveness of the RE methods and their stability as they do not regress as the dataset size increases. In this regard, we recall that RE methods are re-trained from scratch at each iteration and not fine-tuned with new data from the active learning process. Thus, such consistent performances across dataset versions highlight the robustness and reliability of the RE methods.

Regarding GCC extraction, the sentence utility classifier achieves 0.8825 accuracy and 0.8824, 0.8825, and 0.8803 of precision, recall, and F1, respectively. The results highlight the viability of training coarse-grained RE methods using automatically annotated data from DisGeNET and show the effectiveness of the trained method on a manual test set. Thus, the sentence utility classifier is reliable enough to be used as filter on new and heterogeneous sentences gathered from PubMed.

4.3 Knowledge graph completion

4.3.1 Knowledge graphs

We further evaluate the effectiveness of the CORE system on a knowledge base completion task, in which we hold out a portion of an existing KB with associated sentences and we assess CORE ability to recover it. To this end, we hold out from BioXpress the set of 9,636 sentences annotated by DEXTER, and we evaluate the CORE system on them. Note that such sentences are not part of those used to train the CORE RE methods. Given that BioXpress only reports CGE values between cancer and normal samples, we restrict our evaluation to CGE extraction.

As a further experiment, we apply DEXTER to DS2 to evaluate its ability to generalize to heterogeneous sentences, whose syntactic structure can differ from its predefined patterns. Again, we only consider CGE extraction.

4.3.2 RE methods

For BioXpress completion, we use the three versions of the CORE system obtained after each (re)training of the RE methods. On the other hand, since DEXTER is not publicly available, we have re-implemented it with high accuracy, as reported in [Menotti, 2022].

4.3.3 Results

Table 12 reports the CORE system performances on the BioXpress completion task after each (re)training of the RE methods, as well as DEXTER performance on DS2.

Table 12: CORE system performances on the BioXpress completion task after each (re)training of the RE methods. We also report DEXTER performance on DS2.

Dataset	Method	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
BioXpress	CORE0	0.9544	0.9601	0.9544	0.9572
	CORE1	0.9703	0.9831	0.9703	0.9766
	CORE2	0.9706	0.9827	0.9706	0.9766
DS2	DEXTER	0.3256	0.6034	0.3256	0.2882

We can see that each CORE version consistently achieves performances above 0.95 for each measure. In particular, CORE1 improves over CORE0 by about 2% and reaches a performance plateau, where CORE2 also stabilizes with accuracy of 0.9706 and precision, recall, and F1 equal to 0.9827, 0.9706, and 0.9766, respectively. The results show the effectiveness of the CORE system in recovering BioXpress using a limited amount of manual annotations to train the RE methods.

On the other hand, the poor performance of DEXTER on DS2 highlights a lack of flexibility that hampers its applicability to heterogeneous sentences. To further support this intuition, we observe that between precision and recall it is recall to have the worst performance, with a value of 0.3256. This underlines the expert system nature of DEXTER which, although precise, fails to generalize beyond its set of predefined patterns.

4.4 Integration of CORE KG with report-level semantic graphs

To obtain the final KG, we store the following contents into a GraphDB triplestore:

- The CORE ontology;
- The CORE KG;
- The ExaMode ontology;
- The report-level semantic graphs.

Together, these elements represent the text derived ExaMode KG, whose contents have been extracted from scientific literature – via the CORE system – and from medical reports – via the SKET system. Overall, the ExaMode KG contains 30,837,947 statements.

5 Link prediction methods

5.1 Use case

The goal is to predict previously unknown potential associations between genes and diseases based on a given set of already known relations between genes, proteins, and diseases. Note that one way to approach this problem would be to simply skip the use of proteins altogether and use only a set of known associations between genes and diseases to predict new potential associations. However, such a simplified approach would inevitably miss the important properties provided by gene products (proteins). To make use of those properties, we choose to include proteins and their corresponding relations as part of the KG.

Figure 7: Figure 1 Associations between genes and diseases.

5.2 Data description

First, let us begin the data description by defining multigraphs. Formally, a graph $G = (V, E)$ is a multigraph if it can have multiple parallel edges that connect the same end nodes. Furthermore, a KG is a directed multigraph in which nodes $v \in V$ represent entities, and edges $e \in E$ represent relationships between them. A triple (v_1, e, v_2) is referred to as an RDF triple, where $v_1, v_2 \in V$, and $e \in E$.

The ONTO KG has the following properties:

- 16,496,126 RDF triples
- 295,966 unique subjects
- 122,759 unique objects
- 295,975 unique entities
- 12 unique relations.

The UNIPD KG consists entirely of gene-disease associations. Hence, it has the following description:

- 231,098 RDF triples
- 23853 unique subjects (genes)
- 1,767 unique objects (diseases)
- 25,620 unique entities
- 1 unique relation (associatedWith)

Finally, the combined ONTO-UNIPD KG has the following description:

- 16,620,263 unique RDF triples in total
- 305,495 unique subjects
- 122,944 unique objects
- 305,689 unique entities
- 12 unique relations

Table 13 reports the per-relation occurrence statistics within each of the three considered KGs.

5.3 Knowledge graph embedding methods

Let us begin by defining a Knowledge Graph Embedding (KGE). Formally, a KGE is a mapping from entities and relationships to low-dimensional vector spaces. Please note that it is not necessary to have entities and relationships mapping to the same space, or even mapping to spaces with equal dimensions. For instance, in the Hake [Zhang et al., 2019] method, entities and relationships map to ranges with different dimensionality.

In practice, the selection of a KGE method depends on both its computational and theoretical properties. On the computational level, one would be interested in the method’s implementation, the computational infrastructure it requires (e.g., CPU, GPU, and RAM), as well as its running time. As far as theoretical properties are concerned, one would be interested in the method’s ability to preserve different types of relations such as: Symmetric, Antisymmetric, Inverse, Composite, and Hierarchical.

Table 13: Occurrence information for the twelve relations of interest in each KG.

Relation	ONTO	UNIPD	ONTO+UNIPD
https://linkedlifedata.com/property/interactsWith	13,289,752		13,289,752
https://linkedlifedata.com/property/hasMolecularFunction	71,584		71,584
https://linkedlifedata.com/property/hasBiologicalProcess	138,025		138,025
https://linkedlifedata.com/property/hasDomainClassification	1480,630		1,480,630
https://linkedlifedata.com/property/hasCellularComponent	86,200		86,200
http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type	295,972		295,972
https://linkedlifedata.com/property/associatedWith	964,883	231,098	1,089,020
https://linkedlifedata.com/property/participatesInPathway	121,300		121,300
https://linkedlifedata.com/property/encodes	33,376		33,376
https://linkedlifedata.com/property/targetedBy	13,939		13,939
https://linkedlifedata.com/property/hasSymptom	363		363
https://linkedlifedata.com/property/hasLocation	102		102

Below, we provide an overview of the considered KGCE methods.

TorusE [Ebisu and Ichise, 2018]: one of the fastest KGE methods we have today. It was introduced in 2018 as a faster alternative of TransE [Bordes et al., 2013]. TorusE solves the TransE regularization problem by representing entity and relation embeddings as points on a high-dimensional torus. In practice, we use the PyKeen⁸ implementation of TorusE, which allows us to run the method on a single

⁸ <https://github.com/pykeen/pykeen>

CUDA GPU – as this is sufficient for our purposes. From a theoretical point of view, TorusE preserves symmetry, antisymmetry, inversion, and composition.

QuatE [Zhang et al., 2019]: the slowest method among the considered ones. It was introduced in 2019 as a generalization of complex-valued representations. In practice, we use the PyKeen implementation of QuatE. Again, that allows us to run the method on a single CUDA GPU, which is sufficient for our tasks. From a theoretical point of view, QuatE preserves symmetry, antisymmetry, and inversion.

HAKE [Zhang et al., 2020]: the only considered method that explicitly models semantic hierarchical relations. It was introduced in 2020 and has gained popularity since then. It uses a polar coordinate system, and models hierarchy as distance from the origin. Since HAKE is not included in PyKeen, we relied on the GitHub implementation provided by the authors⁹. This implementation allows us to run the method on a single CUDA GPU. From a theoretical point of view, HAKE preserves symmetry, antisymmetry, inversion, composition, and hierarchy.

6 Collection-level data exploration

6.1 CORE KG exploration

We perform some exploratory queries to analyze the contents of the KG produced by CORE. The SPARQL queries used to explore the KG can be found here: <https://github.com/GDAMining/core/blob/main/sparql/example-queries.txt>.

6.1.1 Genes most involved in cancer diseases

Figure 8 illustrates the top ten oncogenes, biomarkers, and tumor suppressor genes associated with cancer. Among the oncogenes, AKT1 emerges as the predominant gene implicated in cancer diseases within the CORE KG. AKT1 exhibits widespread expression in various tissues [Testa and Bellacosa, 2001; Cohen, 2013]. Other known oncogenes are MAPK1 and MAPK3, frequently involved in oncogenesis, tumor progression, and drug resistance [Braicu et al., 2019], and STAT3 [Bromberg et al., 1999]. Regarding biomarkers, there are several known proto-oncogenes such as ERBB2 [Slamon et al., 1989], EGFR [Velu et al., 1987], and BCL2 [Kroemer, 1997]. Proto-oncogenes fit our definition of biomarkers, i.e., genes that show altered expression levels in cancer but do not (yet) have enough evidence to be identified as oncogenes or tumor suppressor genes. A different situation occurs with TP53, which presents an interesting scenario as it is a biomarker and a tumor suppressor gene for many diseases. Over the years, the scientific understanding of TP53 has evolved, initially classifying it as an oncogene [Eliyahu et al., 1984], then recognizing it as a tumor suppressor [Baker et al., 1989], and more recently, under certain conditions, acknowledging its reemergence as an oncogene [Soussi and Wiman, 2015]. Thus, thanks to its probabilistic, fact-centric, and evidence-based approach, the CORE system can capture such a dynamic scenario -- which is proper for scientific discourse.

⁹ <https://github.com/MIRALab-USTC/KGE-HAKE>

Figure 8: The ten most involved genes (and their roles) in cancer diseases. From left to right, the figures present the ten most involved oncogenes, biomarkers, and tumor suppressor genes, respectively.

6.1.2 Most discussed genes, cancer diseases, and facts

Figure 9 presents the genes, diseases, and facts that have garnered the most attention in the scientific literature. Naturally, the most discussed genes align with the ones most involved in cancer diseases. The most discussed topics concerning cancer predominantly revolve around breast, colorectal, prostate, and lung cancer types. This outcome is fitting, as these cancer types are the four most common cancer types worldwide¹⁰. Consequently, the most discussed facts pertain to gene expression-cancer associations involving the aforementioned genes and diseases.

Figure 9: The ten most discussed genes, cancer diseases, and facts within the literature.

6.1.3 Longest-discussed fact in literature

Figure 10 showcases the temporal progression of publications concerning the fact most extensively discussed in the CORE KG, that is (ERBB2, BIOMARKER, Mammary Neoplasms). ERBB2 is a known proto-oncogene that plays an important role in human malignancies and is amplified or overexpressed in approximately 30% of human breast cancers [Slamon et al., 1989]. Therefore, the relevance of ERBB2 in breast cancer well motivates its prominence within the scientific discourse.

¹⁰ <https://www.wcrf.org/cancer-trends/worldwide-cancer-data/>

Figure 10: Temporal progression of publications concerning the longest-discussed fact in literature: (ERBB2, BIOMARKER, Mammary Neoplasms).

6.2 ExaMode KG exploration

We perform some exploratory queries to analyze the contents of the ExaMode KG, composed from the CORE KG and the report-level semantic graphs by SKET.

6.2.1 Find ten most discussed tumor suppressor genes for patient's cancer

Let us assume we have a patient, with patient *ID* = *7c09bfadc0fbdb7d04970b1f1775ad08*, that has been diagnosed with Colon Adenocarcinoma. A clinician might want to search for tumor suppressor genes, which have been discussed within scientific literature, that can inhibit Colon Adenocarcinoma. To do so, the following query can be used:

```

1 PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
2 PREFIX terms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
3 PREFIX exa: <https://w3id.org/examode/ontology/>
4 PREFIX patient: <https://w3id.org/examode/resource/patient/>
5 PREFIX core: <http://gda.dei.unipd.it/cecore/ontology/>
6 PREFIX ncbi: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/>
7 PREFIX umls: <http://linkedlifedata.com/resource/umls/id/>
8
9 SELECT ?gene (COUNT(DISTINCT ?article) as ?numArt)
10 WHERE
11 {
12   patient:7c09bfadc0fbdb7d04970b1f1775ad08 exa:hasClinicalCaseReport ?report.
13   ?report exa:hasOutcome ?outcome.
14   ?outcome exa:positiveType ?class.
15   ?class terms:conformsTo ?umlsID.
16
17   ?fact core:expressedBy ?gene;
18         core:hasType "TSG"^^xsd:string;
19         core:involves ?umlsID;
20         core:supportedBy ?evidence;
21         core:isInformative ?isInfo.
22   FILTER(?isInfo = true)
23   ?evidence core:extractedFrom ?article.
24 }
25 GROUP BY ?gene
26 ORDER BY DESC(?numArt)
27 LIMIT 10

```

Figure 11: Query – the ten most discussed tumor suppressor genes for Colon Adenocarcinoma.

The query provides the following tumor suppressor genes:

	gene	numArt
1	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/7422	"11"xsd:integer
2	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/835	"5"xsd:integer
3	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/5592	"3"xsd:integer
4	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/56484	"3"xsd:integer
5	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/841	"3"xsd:integer
6	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/16168	"2"xsd:integer
7	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/18566	"2"xsd:integer
8	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/18792	"2"xsd:integer
9	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/196	"2"xsd:integer
10	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/1974	"2"xsd:integer

Figure 12: Results – the ten most discussed tumor suppressor genes for Colon Adenocarcinoma.

6.2.2 Find all the available evidence about patient's cancer progression

Let us assume we have a patient, with patient *ID* = *06aac0ca4ea65ca7e635d87d21201d58*, that has been diagnosed with Cervical Adenocarcinoma. A clinician might want to search for all the evidence about oncogenes that are known to aggravate Cervical Adenocarcinoma (i.e., *CCS* = *progression*). In this regard, the following query can be used:

```

1 PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
2 PREFIX terms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
3 PREFIX exa: <https://w3id.org/examode/ontology/>
4 PREFIX patient: <https://w3id.org/examode/resource/patient/>
5 PREFIX core: <http://gda.dei.unipd.it/cecore/ontology/>
6 PREFIX ncbi: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/>
7 PREFIX umls: <http://linkedlifedata.com/resource/umls/id/>
8
9 SELECT ?gene ?sentence ?article
10 WHERE
11 {
12     patient:06aac0ca4ea65ca7e635d87d21201d58 exa:hasClinicalCaseReport ?report.
13     ?report exa:hasOutcome ?outcome.
14     ?outcome exa:positiveType ?class.
15     ?class terms:conformsTo ?umlsID.
16
17     ?fact core:expressedBy ?gene;
18         core:hasType "ONCOGENE"^^xsd:string;
19         core:involves ?umlsID;
20         core:supportedBy ?evidence;
21         core:isInformative ?isInfo.
22     FILTER(?isInfo = true)
23
24     ?evidence core:hasContent ?sentence;
25         core:CCSLabel ?ccs;
26         core:extractedFrom ?article.
27     FILTER(?ccs = 'PROGRESSION'^^xsd:string)
28 }

```

Figure 13: Query – all the available evidence about patient's cancer progression.

The query returns 63 sentences stating that oncogenes aggravate Cervical Adenocarcinoma. A snippet of these results is reported below.

	gene	sentence	article
1	ncbi:5829	"PXN was frequently upregulated and acted as an onco gene via regulating Bcl-2 in cervical cancer, which supports PXN as a potent therapeutic target."	pubmed:29318915
2	ncbi:132625	"Therefore, all our data suggest that REX1 overexpression could play a crucial role in the metastasis and invasion of cervical cancer by upregulating the activity of the JAK2/STAT3 pathway by trans-suppressing SOCS1 expression."	pubmed:31409905
3	ncbi:27429	"Our findings showed that low expression levels of survivin and high expression levels of Omi/HtrA2 in chemotherapy-responsive cervical carcinoma patients significantly increased chemosensitivity."	pubmed:31356194
4	ncbi:10409	"Overexpression of BASP1 promoted the proliferation of cervical cancer and its colony formation ability, accelerated cell cycle progression, and enhanced tumorigenicity."	pubmed:29089860

Figure 14: Results – all the available evidence about patient’s cancer progression.

6.2.3 Find patients that can be affected by BRAF gene

BRAF is a known oncogene for several cancer diseases. A clinician working on BRAF might be interested to find patients for which BRAF might act as an oncogene and contact them for enrollment in clinical trials. To find these patients, together with the associated reports, the following query can be used:

```

+ 1 PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
2 PREFIX terms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
3 PREFIX exa: <https://w3id.org/examode/ontology/>
4 PREFIX core: <http://gda.dei.unipd.it/cecere/ontology/>
5 PREFIX ncbi: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/>
6 PREFIX umls: <http://linkedlifedata.com/resource/umls/id/>
7
8 SELECT * WHERE
+ 9 {
+ 10 {
+ 11     SELECT DISTINCT ?patient ?report ?usecase
+ 12     WHERE
+ 13     {
+ 14         ?fact core:expressedBy ncbi:673;
+ 15         core:hasType "ONCOGENE"^^xsd:string;
+ 16         core:involves ?umlsID;
+ 17         core:isInformative ?isInfo.
+ 18         FILTER(?isInfo = true)
+ 19
+ 20         ?class terms:conformsTo ?umlsID.
+ 21         ?outcome exa:positiveType ?class.
+ 22         ?report exa:hasOutcome ?outcome;
+ 23         a ?usecase.
+ 24
+ 25         ?patient exa:hasClinicalCaseReport ?report.
+ 26     }
+ 27 }
+ 28 UNION
+ 29 {
+ 30     SELECT DISTINCT ?patient ?report ?usecase
+ 31     WHERE
+ 32     {
+ 33         ?fact core:expressedBy ncbi:673;
+ 34         core:hasType "ONCOGENE"^^xsd:string;
+ 35         core:involves ?umlsID;
+ 36         core:isInformative ?isInfo.
+ 37         FILTER(?isInfo = true)
+ 38
+ 39         ?class terms:conformsTo ?umlsID.
+ 40         ?outcome a ?class.
+ 41         ?report exa:hasOutcome ?outcome;
+ 42         a ?usecase.
+ 43
+ 44         ?patient exa:hasClinicalCaseReport ?report.
+ 45     }
+ 46 }
+ 47 }

```

Figure 15: Query – patients that can be affected by BRAF gene.

The results of the query comprise 2,518 medical reports, of which 1,998 refer to colon cancer and 520 to lung cancer. A snippet of the results is reported below.

	patient	report	usecase
1	https://w3id.org/examode/resource/patient/5c-b78732ce25dfda85dd234237fa41f8	https://w3id.org/examode/resource/report/5c-b78732ce25dfda85dd234237fa41f8	ontology:LungClinicalCaseReport
2	https://w3id.org/examode/resource/patient/64b-d74dbf8801051792a3d682c2a3764	https://w3id.org/examode/resource/report/64b-d74dbf8801051792a3d682c2a3764	ontology:LungClinicalCaseReport
3	https://w3id.org/examode/resource/patient/6d-b851986a48b80f82684e8c5d688448	https://w3id.org/examode/resource/report/6d-b851986a48b80f82684e8c5d688448	ontology:LungClinicalCaseReport
4	https://w3id.org/examode/resource/patient/78bcd4-d4f35b3beb2d3577f1531946512f	https://w3id.org/examode/resource/report/78bcd4-d4f35b3beb2d3577f1531946512f	ontology:LungClinicalCaseReport

Figure 16: Results – patients that can be affected by BRAF gene.

6.3 COREKB

To make the KB of CORE easily accessible and interrogable we developed COREKB [Giachelle et al., 2023], an intuitive and easy-to-use web-based platform for searching scientific facts over gene expression-cancer associations. COREKB provides a streamlined interface for searching either using natural language queries or by exploiting structured facets providing autocomplete facilities; it is designed to simplify information access and search of scientific facts targeting healthcare stakeholders (i.e., clinicians, physicians, and researchers). COREKB aims at presenting the user a comprehensive overview of the scientific evidence supporting a medical fact, fully connected with ontology-based entities and well-defined literature resources. In addition, COREKB provides the user a quantitative comparison of the possible gene-cancer associations related to a specific fact, thus enabling users to assess the degree of agreement among the evidence support. COREKB is publicly available at <https://gda.dei.unipd.it> along with a demonstration video (<http://bit.ly/corekbsearch>) presenting its features. The platform provides a streamlined interface for searching and exploring knowledge about gene expression-cancer associations. COREKB allows users to query the system using either natural language queries or facets, enabling search for both entities and facts easily. In this regard, COREKB provides several features (e.g., infometrics and entity cards) to support specialized users, such as medical researchers and clinicians, who are interested in searching for knowledge about gene expression-cancer associations quickly and without requiring the exact terminology or entity identifiers. As a distinctive trait, COREKB embraces a fact-oriented approach, which aims at providing users with a comprehensive overview of the key information concerning each fact. The overview provided consists of aggregated data including (i) the gene class distribution among the sentences extracted from the scientific literature; (ii) the number of supporting and conflicting sentences (iii) and the number of supporting publications per year, enabling users to assess the consensus supporting a fact. In summary, COREKB offers a powerful platform for comprehensive knowledge discovery in precision medicine.

Despite the importance of providing a fact-level overview for a scientific claim – i.e., showing aggregated information describing a scientific fact overall, by combining data coming from several scientific publications and resources – most of the state-of-the-art methods and tools only focuses on providing point-wise sentence-level information – thus not presenting the big-picture understanding. COREKB aims to fill this gap by providing a comprehensive, literature- supported overview for each scientific fact. In this way, COREKB differs from other approaches and platforms such as DEXTER, OncoMX, OncoSearch, DisGeNET, and BioKB. DEXTER is a text mining approach designed for associations extraction from scientific literature; it provides a search endpoint enabling users to search for gene-cancer pairs with no support for natural language queries. OncoMX consists of a unified interface providing access to multiple datasets; it is not intended for extensive literature mining. OncoSearch focuses on providing users search capabilities, (e.g., faceted search facilities), targeting sentences where gene expression changes are detected with respect to cancer cases. However, it provides

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no support for natural language queries, entity cards, infometrics, and other information concerning the supporting evidence. DisGeNET is a well-established database of gene-disease associations that can be searched and accessed through a structured/faceted interface; it is limited to sentence-level gene-disease associations – i.e., associations established by considering different individual sentences involving gene-disease associations (no aggregated high-level information) – thus not providing aggregated fact level information on the gene-disease pairs of interest. Instead, BioKB [Biryukov et al., 2017] is a web-based tool for entity/fact search enabling users to access, through a structured interface, the semantic information concerning biomedical publications; it provides no support for natural language queries but focuses instead on the exploration/visualization of the relationships among entities according to the underlying KB.

6.3.1 COREKB Search Platform

Figure 1 shows, on the left side, the CORE system, whereas, on the right side, the COREKB architecture along with its components.

Figure 17 Overview of the CORE system (left side) and the COREKB architectural components (right side).

COREKB consists of several components including (i) a React-based web interface for the front-end; (ii) a Django-based business logic for the back-end providing support for REST APIs and services; (iii) a PostgreSQL database aligned with an instance of the Virtuoso RDF triple store for storing the KB data; (iv) a Redis server broker for efficient in-memory data store and access and (v) a Python-based search component that performs NERD on entity mentions in user queries and then performs a structured search in the database to retrieve the matching facts and the related information. To this end, the search component relies on a Redis in-memory dictionary of entities returning for each entity name and synonyms the corresponding unique identifier. When a user-provided query is entered in the system, the search component assigns a score to each entity that is maximum in case of an exact match or proportional to the number of matching terms in case of a partial match. To avoid favoring long-named

entities at the disadvantage of those with short names, the score is discounted proportionally to the entity name's length. If a single entity is recognized, all the related facts are ordered by scientific evidence support.

Similarly, if multiple entities are identified, the facts regarding the most matching gene-cancer pairs are promoted in the ranking of results. It's worth noting that COREKB is not limited to human gene-cancer pairs, instead, it contains facts regarding any living organism. Nevertheless, human-specific genes are ranked on top.

Figure 18 CoreKB Search Engine Results Page (SERP) for the query “MAPK1 oncogene melanoma”. The retrieved facts are organized as cards (A) providing information about the gene (3), cancer (4), and their relationship (2). The fact illustrated in the figure is “ MAPK1 is an oncogene for melanoma” (1). Regarding this fact, there are 64 supporting sentences and 43 conflicting sentences (7). The supporting sentences indicate MAPK1 as an oncogene for melanoma whereas the conflicting ones propose two different gene classes: biomarker (28 sentences in favor) and tumor suppressor (15 sentences in favor). Since the majority of the scientific evidence available propose MAPK1 as an oncogene, the fact is considered reliable. Note that the gene MAPK1 is a human gene, as indicated between parentheses (9) in the card (B). card (B) reports the entity cards describing the gene and the disease. The entity cards describe the gene (10) and the disease (11, 12) in depth presenting global information that can be clicked and explored by the user.

COREKB

A
1
MAPK1 (Homo sapiens)
2

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/5594>

3 Full name: mitogen-activated protein kinase 1

4 Gene type: protein-coding

5 Synonyms: ERK, ERK-2, ERK2, ERT1, MAPK2, NS13, P42MAPK, PRKM1, PRKM2, p38, p40, p41, p41mapk, p42-MAPK

6 Other designations: mitogen-activated protein kinase 1|MAP kinase 1|MAP kinase 2|MAPK 2|extracellular signal-regulated kinase 2|mitogen-activated protein kinase 2|protein tyrosine kinase ERK2

7 Last modified date: 2022-10-09

8 Summary: This gene encodes a member of the MAP kinase family. MAP kinases, also known as extracellular signal-regulated kinases (ERKs), act as an integration point for multiple biochemical ...

9 MAPK1 is an **oncogene** for **75** diseases, a **biomarker** for **49** diseases, a **tumor suppressor gene** for **13** diseases, and has an **uncertain** role for **86** diseases.

10 MAPK1 gene-class distribution

Gene Class	Count
Oncogene	75
Biomarker	49
Tumor suppressor gene	13
Uncertain	86

B
11
Sentences with MAPK1 involved
12

Scientific fact	Gene ...	Disease label	13 Gene cl...	Extracted from	14 Journal	15 Publication year
Filter...	Filter...	Filter...	oncogene	Filter...	Filter...	Filter...
MAPK1 is an oncogene for Malignant Glioma	MAPK1	Malignant Glioma	oncogene	https://pubmed.n...	J Mol Neuro...	2018
MAPK1 is an oncogene for Sporadic Retinoblastoma	MAPK1	Sporadic Retinoblastoma	oncogene	https://pubmed.n...	Int J Mol Me...	2019
MAPK1 is an oncogene for Neoplasm Metastasis	MAPK1	Neoplasm Metastasis	oncogene	https://pubmed.n...	Cancer Med	2013
MAPK1 is an oncogene for Malignant Glioma	MAPK1	Malignant Glioma	oncogene	https://pubmed.n...	Oncogene	2017
MAPK1 is an oncogene for Malignant Glioma	MAPK1	Malignant Glioma	oncogene	https://pubmed.n...	Front Oncol...	2019
MAPK1 is an oncogene for Neoplasm Metastasis	MAPK1	Neoplasm Metastasis	oncogene	https://pubmed.n...	J Exp Clin C...	2019
MAPK1 is an oncogene for Malignant Glioma	MAPK1	Malignant Glioma	oncogene	https://pubmed.n...	World J Sur...	2012
MAPK1 is an oncogene for Malignant Glioma	MAPK1	Malignant Glioma	oncogene	https://pubmed.n...	Oncotarget	2015

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Figure 19 Landing page for the gene MAPK1. The interface consists of two cards; the first (A) reports gene-specific information, while the second (B) shows the sentences where MAPK1 is involved, according to the user-specified column filters and sorting. In the figure, only the sentences where MAPK1 is involved as an oncogene are shown due to the filtering on the Gene class column (13). Gene/cancer mentions are highlighted in the sentence text respectively in blue

and orange. For each sentence, it is shown information about the publication from which it is extracted, such as the PubMed URL, the journal name (14), and the publication year (15).

Figure 20 (A) Pop-up reporting the information concerning the sentence clicked in the table in Figure 19.B by the user. (B) Landing page for the sentence corresponding to the permanent link identifier clicked by the user.

The COREKB platform enables users to search for factual information related to gene-cancer associations supported by scientific literature, as well as entities such as genes and cancer diseases. Users can search using free-text or structured search facilities with autocomplete features. The interface allows users to switch between the two search modes via the settings menu and provides clickable sample queries to demonstrate the system's capabilities. The search results are presented in cards that display gene class, cancer label, statistics on supporting and conflicting sentences, key examples of supporting and conflicting sentences, and bibliometrics on the number of supporting publications per year. The reliability of the fact is indicated by a circle that is colored differently according to the informativeness and reliability of the fact - i.e., green for reliable facts, gray for facts missing proper support, and red for unreliable facts. On the right side of each fact card, specific information about the gene and cancer involved is presented, including links to the corresponding entries in the NCBI and Linked Life Data¹¹ platforms. Users can access additional quantitative and aggregated information on dedicated landing pages, including related facts and supporting and conflicting sentences. The landing page for a particular gene displays all the available information about the gene, including its symbol, full name, type, synonyms, designations, summary, and gene class distribution for different cancer diseases. The sentences involving the gene are presented in a table that users can filter and sort arbitrarily. Action buttons enable users to expand or collapse each card and choose the columns to be shown in the sentence table. Figure 20 shows the landing page for a given entity, that is, in this case the human gene MAPK1. The interface comprises two major cards (A, B). The first card (A) displays comprehensive information about the gene, including its symbol (1), full name (3), type (4), synonyms (5), designations (6), last modified date (7), summary (8), and the gene class distribution – i.e., the role

¹¹ <http://linkedlifedata.com>

of the gene in a specific gene-cancer association which can assume one of alternatives *oncogene*, *biomarker*, *tumor suppressor gene* – for several cancer diseases presented both as a textual statement (9) and depicted also in a horizontal bar chart (10). It is worth noting that all the numbers reported in the textual statement are clickable and allows the users to visualize on a new tab the specific gene-cancer associations of interest (e.g., for which cancer diseases the MAPK1 gene is indicated to be an oncogene). To save space on the interface, long textual information such as the gene summary is truncated by default, but it can be expanded or collapsed by clicking on the dedicated button after the ellipsis.

The second card (B) provides a list of sentences related to the gene. The sentences are presented in a dynamic table that allows users to filter and sort them according to their preferences. For instance, in Figure 19, only the sentences where *MAPK1* is reported as an oncogene are displayed because of the user-provided value “oncogene” for the “Gene class” column (13). In case of long sentences, users can either (i) resize columns; (ii) going over with the mouse on a sentence to view the full sentence text in a small tool-tip or (iii) click on the sentence to visualize it in a separate pop-up. Moreover, there are two buttons reported on the top-right corner of each card so that users can expand/collapse each card alternatively to fit the full-screen size (2, 12) and choose the columns to be shown in the sentence table (11). Most of the information reported in the sentence table of Figure 19.B are clickable, including (i) the sentence; (ii) the scientific fact; (iii) the gene; (iv) the disease; (v) the PubMed link to the publication from which the sentence has been extracted and (vi) the publication journal. When the user clicks on a sentence, a pop-up appears to show all the relevant information concerning the sentence such as the sentence identifier, its textual content, the gene, the cancer disease, and their relationship. Figure 20 shows the informative pop-up for the sentence’s fact “MAPK1 is an oncogene for melanoma”, which is reported on top of the window card. Then, the pop-up reports other information concerning the sentence, the gene, the cancer disease, and their association in separated collapsible menus. Each sentence and fact in COREKB is univocally identified with a permanent URL enabling point-wise access to the information specific for an individual resource. Indeed, when the user clicks on the sentence identifier in Figure 20.A the corresponding landing page for the sentence is shown, as depicted in Figure 20.B. Note that in the landing page, users can access provenance information about the sentence, that is, the PubMed URL to the original publication and a link to the corresponding journal entry in the SCImago Portal¹². Similarly, when users click on a fact the corresponding landing page for the scientific claim is shown providing a holistic perspective enabling to assess overall the literature consensus among the supporting/conflicting evidences.

7 Usability and User study

To evaluate COREKB in terms of usability, user experience and satisfaction we conducted a user study that permitted us also to collect feedback from different domain and technical experts to improve COREKB accordingly. Specifically, we conducted the user study in an asynchronous fashion, so that the participants could start it when they preferred. In this regard, we provided the participants a private link to an online form where they can answer a set of predefined questions and provide their feedback. Moreover, we divided the user study into two parts, designed to measure respectively the *learnability* and *usability* of COREKB. The learnability part focused on assessing the confidence and the awareness of the users with respect to accomplishing a set of predefined tasks such as identifying which concepts are related to a specific mention or the concepts from which a specific label has been generated. Then, the collected answers of each user have been compared with the correct ones, in order to assess the user proficiency with COREKB with respect to searching purposes. Secondly, we evaluated COREKB in terms of usability and user satisfaction using the System Usability Scale (SUS), which is widely used and is considered an industry standard for assessing usability [Brooke et al. 1996]. Finally, we collected

¹² <https://www.scimagojr.com>

useful opinions and suggestions from the participating experts in order to comprehend the key points of strength as well as the features to be revised so that to improve the system overall.

To support users in the comprehension of the user study, we provided an introductory video for COREKB (4 min.) available at: <http://bit.ly/corekbsearch>.

In the very beginning of the user study, we asked the participants to provide their current position/occupation by choosing one or more options among: Professor/Teacher, Healthcare professional, Industry, Master Student, PhD Student, Postdoctoral Researcher, Junior Researcher; they could also specify a different one. Overall, thirteen participants have been involved in the user study distributed among Professor/Teacher (23.1%), Biology expert (15.4%), PhD student (15.4%), Postdoctoral Researcher (15.4%), Junior Researcher (15.4%), and Healthcare professional (7.7%). Besides, we asked the participants to specify their primary domains of expertise by choosing among the options: *Biology, Computational Pathology, Computer Engineering, Computer Science, Data Science, Digital Pathology, Life Sciences, Medicine, Psychology*; they could also indicate an appropriate domain not already listed. Among all, the major domains of expertise specified were Computer Engineering (46.2%), Data Science (30.8%), Computer Science (30.8%), Biology (23.1%), Computational Pathology (15.4%), and Life Sciences (15.4%) as shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21 Primary domains of expertise of the participants involved in the user study. “Immun...” stands for “Immunology” and “Metab...” for “Metabolism”.

For what concerns instead the learnability part of the user study, we asked the participants to perform five tasks related to searching for scientific facts and gene-cancer expression entities and then to answer a set of closed-form questions. In this regard, we asked the participants to answer the following questions:

- Which of the following diseases involves the human gene BRAF as a biomarker?
 - Multiple possible answers among the options: *Malignant neoplasm of prostate, Uveal melanoma, Adenocarcinoma of colon, Brain Neoplasms*.
 - Correct option: *Uveal melanoma*
- Which of the following genes is an oncogene for melanoma?

- One possible answer among the options: *SAMMSON*, *erbb2*, *BRCA1*, *CASC9*.
 - Correct option: *SAMMSON*
3. What is the number of diseases having BRAF as an oncogene?
 - One possible answer among the options: 14, 100, 28, *None of the previous*
 - Correct option: 14
 4. What is the number of sentences supporting the scientific fact: "BRAF is a biomarker for Metastatic melanoma"?
 - One possible answer among the options: 2, 25, 10, *None of the previous*
 - Correct option: 2
 5. What is the number of supporting publications in 2022 for the scientific fact: "*ERBB2 is a biomarker for Mammary Neoplasms*"?
 - One possible answer among the options: 5, 25, 12, *None of the previous*
 - Correct option: 25

The first question was answered correctly by all the participants, despite half of the participants also included in the answer the *Malignant neoplasm of prostate* disease whereas almost a third of them also included the *Adenocarcinoma of colon* disease. For what concerns the second question, it was answered correctly by the majority of the participants (69.2%), although one third of them answered wrong. Instead, all the participants answered correctly the third question. For what concerns the fourth question, it was answered correctly by almost all the participants (92.3%), only one participant answered wrong. Similarly, the last question was answered correctly by most of the participants (84.6%).

To better understand the reasoning process used to answer, we asked the participants to briefly describe the procedure followed for searching for scientific facts and gene-cancer expression entities. In addition, we asked the participants to describe the searching features used (e.g., free-text search, structured/faceted search) to discover the information of interest. The answers collected confirm that most of the participants correctly understood how to search for gene-cancer expressions, relationships, and the related entities. Indeed, some of the explanations collected follows:

- “*both free-text search (for question 2) and structured search for all the other questions*”
- “*I have used structured search to identify the provided entities/predicates and looking for the missing ones. When I was unable to find them through structured search, I relied on free-text search for a less constrained search.*”
- “*I clicked on the links and searched for the number indicating the right response. For the first question, I searched in the free text field the name of the disease.*”
- “*Search the information is easy: just typing a peculiar disease allows to retrieve a lot of information. The preview is optimal to have a high-level idea, but it is also possible to look for specific information, about publication or about a very specific aspect.*”

For what concerns instead the second part – i.e., usability and satisfaction - of the user study, we asked the users to answer a set of twelve questions, part of them necessary to evaluate usability of the system according to the SUS scale. It is worth noting that all the questions can be answered by choosing a number in the range 1-5 (extremes included) as for the Likert scale. The complete list of the questions follows:

1. “*In your opinion, searching effectively for reliable scientific facts is relevant for the stakeholders (researchers, physicians, biomedical experts)?*”

2. *“In your opinion, is COREKB effective for searching reliable medical facts and checking their provenance?”*
3. *“Would you like to use COREKB for searching for reliable scientific facts?”*
4. *“In your opinion, is COREKB unnecessarily complex?”*
5. *“Do you consider the interface of COREKB intuitive and easy-to-use?”*
6. *“Do you think the support of a technician is necessary to use COREKB?”*
7. *“Do you think the various functions of COREKB are well integrated?”*
8. *“Do you think that there is too much inconsistency in COREKB?”*
9. *“In your opinion, would most of the stakeholders (researchers, biomedical experts) learn to use COREKB quickly?”*
10. *“According to your experience with COREKB, was it cumbersome to use?”*
11. *“According to your experience with COREKB, did you feel confident when using it?”*
12. *“According to your experience with COREKB, did you need to learn a lot of things before using it?”*

7.1 Results

In this section we report the answers collected for the questions above as well as some statistics about the scores obtained.

1. All the participants consider the task of searching effectively for reliable scientific facts as relevant for the stakeholders – i.e., researchers, physicians, biomedical experts. This fact is highlighted by the scores provided by the participants, that are all equal or greater than four (mean: 4.69; median: 5; st. dev.: 0.48).
2. All the participants consider COREKB effective for searching reliable medical facts and checking their provenance. Indeed, all the participants provided a score equal or greater than four (mean: 4.62; median: 5; st. dev.: 0.51).
3. Most of the participants would use COREKB for searching for reliable scientific facts. Indeed, the majority (92.31%) provided a score equal or greater than four, whereas just one participant provided a score equal to three (mean: 4.46; median: 4.50; st. dev.: 0.66).
4. Most of the participants (76.92%) do not consider COREKB unnecessarily complex and provide a score lower than three. Besides, the rest of the participants (23.08%) do not take a strong position (score equal to three). Overall, the distribution tends to support the fact that COREKB is not unnecessarily complex (mean: 1.85; median: 2; st. dev.: 0.80).
5. Most of the participants (84.62%) state that the interface of COREKB is intuitive and easy-to-use (score equal or greater than four) whereas two participants do not take a strong position (score equal to three). Overall, the distribution tends to support the fact that the interface of COREKB is intuitive and easy-to-use (mean: 4.15; median: 4; st. dev.: 0.69).
6. Most of the participants (84.62%) indicate that the support of a technician is not necessary to use COREKB (score lower than three), whereas two participants consider the support of a technician necessary (score equal or greater than four). Overall, the distribution tends to support the fact that there is no necessity of technical assistance when using COREKB (mean: 1.92; median: 2.00; st. dev.: 1.04).
7. All the participants consider the various functions of COREKB well integrated, by providing a score equal or greater than four (mean: 4.62; median: 5; st. dev.: 0.51).
8. Most of the participants (76.92%) state that there is no prominent inconsistency in COREKB (score lower than three). Instead, others (23.08%) do not take a strong position (score equal to three). Overall, the distribution tends to exclude the presence of prominent inconsistencies (mean: 1.69; median: 1.50; st. dev.: 0.85).

9. Almost the totality (92.31%) of the participants agrees on the fact that the stakeholders (i.e., researchers, physicians, biomedical experts) can learn to use COREKB quickly (mean: 4.54; median: 5; st. dev.: 0.66).
10. Most of the participants (84,62%) indicates that COREKB was not cumbersome to use (score lower than three). However, one participant indicates the opposite (score higher than three). Overall, the distribution tends to support the fact that COREKB is not cumbersome to use (mean: 1.92; median: 2; st. dev.: 1.12).
11. Most of the participants (76.92%) state that they feel confident when using COREKB (score higher than three). Instead, two participants do not take a strong position (score equal to three), whereas one participant indicates that does not feel confident when using it. Overall, the distribution tends to support the fact that users feel confident when using COREKB (mean: 4.08; median: 4; st. dev.: 0.95).
12. Almost all the participants (92.31%) state that they did not need to learn a lot of notions before using COREKB (score lower than three), despite one participant do not take a strong position (score equal to three). Overall, the distribution suggests that there is no necessity for the stakeholders to learn a lot of notions and prerequisites before using COREKB (mean: 1.46; median: 1; st. dev.: 0.66).

In addition, we computed the SUS score from the answers to questions [3-12] of each participant and then we average them over the total number of participants. Hence, the average SUS score obtained is equal to 82.5, which indicates that the usability of COREKB is quite good.

7.2 Final remarks

COREKB is a web-based search platform designed to provide users with reliable scientific facts on gene expression-cancer associations. The platform offers natural language query support as well as structured facet search features integrated with autocomplete facilities. As a distinguishing feature, COREKB focuses on presenting fact-oriented information rather than adopting a sentence-level approach, where only single, independent results are presented. To this end, COREKB combines multiple aggregated information from several literature resources either supporting or conflicting with the scientific claim of interest. This approach offers a comprehensive overview of the scientific evidence associated with a given fact. Moreover, COREKB provides users with a quantitative comparison of the possible gene-cancer associations, making it easier to determine if there is a consensus on a specific gene's role. Although COREKB focus is on gene expression-cancer associations, its model can be adapted and reused to accommodate other types of relationships with the appropriate modifications. The platform aims to support clinicians and researchers by providing fast search, access, and consultation of reliable scientific findings along with validating literature evidence. Hence, simplifying knowledge discovery and promoting a serendipity-oriented perspective.

From the first part of the user study focused on measuring the learnability of COREKB, it was observed that the great majority of users successfully completed the assigned tasks. Furthermore, the explanations provided by the participants to support their answers indicated a clear understanding of the reasoning process required to interact with COREKB's interface. These findings align with the results obtained from the questionnaire designed to measure the usability and user satisfaction of COREKB. The questionnaire revealed a significant finding: all participants acknowledged the importance of effectively searching for reliable scientific facts, particularly for stakeholders such as researchers, physicians, and biomedical experts. Their responses to question 3 also indicated their intention to use COREKB for searching for reliable scientific facts. Moreover, the results obtained for questions 9 and 12 affirmed that the stakeholders could quickly learn to use COREKB without requiring extensive prior knowledge or prerequisites. Additionally, the questionnaire results, particularly in response to question 2, demonstrated that all participants considered COREKB to be effective in searching for reliable medical facts and checking their provenance.

8 Conclusion

This Deliverable serves as a comprehensive summary of the outcomes of Task 2.3 and the overall achievements of Work Package 2 (WP2) within the ExaMode project. The focus lies on the presentation of the final KB pertaining to gene expression-cancer associations, as well as the introduction of the CORE KG knowledge discovery system.

The CORE KG offers users access to an extensive collection of knowledge, which is available in both human- and machine-readable formats. The information originates from scientific literature and is connected to the ExaMode semantic graphs extracted from medical reports accessible to the ExaMode consortium.

The public data extracted from the literature are openly released by CORE KG, allowing wider accessibility. Conversely, the private data remain accessible exclusively to consortium members. Both datasets can be explored using SPARQL queries and various tools developed throughout the project and presented in Deliverables 2.1, 2.2, and 2.4.

This Deliverable serves as a comprehensive culmination of the efforts invested in WP2, highlighting the significant progress made in consolidating the KB and developing the CORE KG system, ultimately enhancing knowledge dissemination and facilitating further research within and beyond the ExaMode project.

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Annexes

Link Prediction Results

In this Section we report the numerical results of the experiments we conducted on the link prediction task.

Dataset split

For the ONTO KG, we use the following split:

- 15,669,951 RDF triples for training
- 100,000 RDF triples for validation
- 726,175 RDF triples for test

For the ONTO+UNIPD KG, we use the following split:

- 15,782,949 RDF triples for training
- 100,000 RDF triples for validation
- 737,314 RDF triples for test

Hyperparameters optimization

Hyperparameter optimization for KGE methods usually involves the use of exhaustive grid search over the set of hyperparameters. However, our initial experiments indicated that exhaustive grid search would be computationally prohibitive given the sizes of our datasets. Thus, we decided to use the ray[tune] library [Liaw et al., 2018] with the Hyperopt [Bergstra et al., 2013] asynchronous distributed hyperparameter optimization package. Hyperopt employs a probabilistic search algorithm known as Tree-structured Parzen Estimators (TPE) [Bergstra et al., 2011]. In addition, we use a fixed number of epochs per TPE point, rather than early stopping. We use 100 epochs per point for the faster TorusE method, and 10 epochs per point for the slower QuatE and HAKE. Finally, we use a multi-GPU setup for asynchronous hyper-parameter optimization with four CUDA GPUs.

Numerical experiments

ONTO KG:

Table 14: Hyperparameters for each TorusE model.

Model	Learning rate	Embedding dimension	Loss margin	Num negs per pos	Batch size	Epochs
TorusE 1	0.0009844	294	1	1	8192	1000
TorusE 2	0.002	300	1	20	8192	1000
TorusE 3	0.002	1000	1	20	8192	1000

Table 15: Metrics for each TorusE model.

Model	MR	MRR	Hits@1	Hits@3	Hits@10
TorusE 1	2892.0363	0.0770371	0.0533721	0.0811374	0.1185836
TorusE 2	2901.1865	0.0820758	0.058627	0.0863813	0.1228009
TorusE 3	1420.7918	0.1241468	0.081797	0.131113	0.2021482

Table 16: Hyperparameters for each QuatE model.

Model	Learning rate	Embedding dimension	Num negs per pos	Reg. P	Reg. weight	Batch size	Epochs
QuatE 1	0.001	200	20	2	0.05	1024	100
QuatE 2	0.001	250	20	2	0.05	1024	1000
QuatE 3	0.001	1000	20	2	0.05	1024	100

Table 17: Metrics for each QuatE model.

Model	MR	MRR	Hits@1	Hits@3	Hits@10
QuatE 1	2559.7693	0.0811626	0.0450807	0.0836761	0.1461555
QuatE 2	2607.6403	0.0728325	0.0356814	0.0748882	0.1410617
QuatE 3	1782.9227	0.0809105	0.0336234	0.0851606	0.1724928

Table 18: Hyperparameters for each HAKE model.

Model	Learning rate	Loss margin	Hidden dimension	Num negs per pos	α	Modulus weight	Phase weight	Epochs
HAKE 1	0.0005	12	250	256	3	1.5	5	100
HAKE 2	0.0001	10	300	128	4.5	1.5	2.5	100
HAKE 3	0.0002	10	400	256	2.5	2.5	2	100

Table 19: Metrics for each HAKE model.

Model	MR	MRR	Hits@1	Hits@3	Hits@10
HAKE 1	838.57553	0.158127	0.074707	0.192438	0.310433
HAKE 2	1042.2043	0.188764	0.101701	0.234638	0.335243

HAKE 3	644.36991	0.192033	0.081118	0.242899	0.402987
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ONTO + UNIPD KG:

Table 20: Hyperparameters for TorusE with ONTO+UNIPD data.

Model	Learning rate	Embedding dimension	Loss margin	Num negs per pos	Batch size	Epochs
TorusE	0.0005	900	2	5	8192	1000

Table 21: Hyperparameters for QuatE with ONTO+UNIPD data.

Model	Learning rate	Embedding dimension	Num negs per pos	Reg. P	Reg. weight	Batch size	Epochs
QuatE	0.001	800	10	2	0.05	1024	100

Table 22: Hyperparameters for HAKE with ONTO+UNIPD data.

Model	Learning rate	Loss margin	Hidden dimension	Num negs per pos	α	Modulus weight	Phase weight	Epochs
HAKE	0.0001	8	400	256	2	4	1.5	100

Table 23: Metrics for each model for ONTO+UNIPD data.

Model	MR	MRR	Hits@1	Hits@3	Hits@10
TorusE	2909.3759	0.0878901	0.0641207	0.0926641	0.1288039
QuatE	2192.9875	0.0730188	0.0321031	0.0764525	0.1506974
HAKE	1960.5443	0.189546	0.110103	0.231620	0.322257